

MEDINA

Deliverable D3.1

Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v1

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Abstract:	This deliverable will encompass techniques how to integrate different tools to gather and manage trustworthy evidence on various levels as well as how to ensure the trustworthiness of evidence across the life-cycle, i.e. using blockchain/DLT. There will be three iterations of the deliverable, an initial prototype, reflecting an early stage of integration in the technical framework (D3.1.x), the second release will be based on a refinement of the technical architecture, finally the third iteration will reflect the implementation of the use cases. This deliverable is the result of Task 3.1 and Task 3.5.
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Terms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAB	Conformance Assessment Body
CI/CD	Continuous integration / continuous deployment
CIS	Center for Internet Security
CPG	Code Property Graph
CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DAST	Dynamic application security testing
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KR	Key Result
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection System
NIDS	network-based IDS
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NLP	Natural language processing
OSSEC	Open Source HIDS SECURITY
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PCI DSS	Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard
REST	Representational State Transfer
SaaS	Software as a Service
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
UI	User Interface
VAT	Vulnerability Assessment Tool
VM	Virtual Machine <input type="text" value="User Interface"/>

Executive Summary

This document aims at presenting work related to the architecture of the MEDINA evidence management tool [KR4] and the trustworthiness management system that aims at ensuring that all evidence and assessment results are secured. This is done by means of smart contracts.

The deliverable introduces the current state of practice in the domains leveraged by the MEDINA evidence management tool, namely the security performance configuration of cloud workloads, the security assessment of computing infrastructure, more specifically in regard to vulnerability assessment and intrusion detection, and in the information data-flows in cloud applications.

The architecture, data model and sequence diagrams are also proposed, extending the models already presented in D5.1 [1].

While the technical details of the tools that compose the MEDINA evidence management tool [KR4] are presented in D3.4 [2], in this document the main ideas and motivation have been presented. Moreover, the coverage of the requirements of assurance level high coming from the draft candidate EUCS scheme version of December 2020 [3] has been matched with the different tools comprising the MEDINA evidence management tool. In addition to that, the future functionalities that should be added in order to comply with the EUCS requirements have also been identified.

The functional and technical details of the trustworthiness management system, how it fits into the MEDINA framework, the architecture and description of the prototype, and how it is delivered have also been presented. This is a novelty of MEDINA.

Finally, and even if MEDINA focuses mostly on the automated monitoring and the assurance level high of the EUCS, CSPs may still struggle in the basic level, especially smaller ones. The checklist presented in Section 6 is aimed at this small CSPs so that they are guided in their self – assessment and can know which kind of evidence they shall provide to the CABs when doing the third-party assessment. This is an innovation brought in by MEDINA.

Future versions of this document will include updated versions of the trustworthiness management system of gathered evidence with new functionalities, as well as the checklist presented in Section 6 and Appendix C: Self-assessment questionnaires. A checklist for higher levels of assurance will also be explored. Furthermore, compositional certification and how this can be addressed in the cloud supply chain will also be investigated.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document presents the first version of the tools used for trustworthy evidence management in MEDINA and the architecture of the MEDINA evidence management tool [KR4]. The technical details of said tools are in D3.4 [2].

1.2 Document structure

Section 1 is the current section.

Section 2 presents the current state of practice in the assessment of security performance configuration of cloud workloads, assessment of computing infrastructure and information of data flows, comparing them briefly to the solutions that MEDINA aims to develop.

Section 3 is devoted to the structural description of the MEDINA Evidence Management Tool. The MEDINA evidence management tool is composed of Clouditor, Wazuh, the Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT), the organizational evidence gathering tool, and Codyze. They are all convened into an orchestrator that is integrated in Clouditor. This section explains the architecture, the data model and the sequence diagrams.

Section 4 briefly introduces the tools that comprise the MEDINA Evidence Management Tool and demonstrates the coverage of said tools with respect to the requirements of assurance level high identified from the draft candidate scheme EUCS (version December 2020) that require an automated monitoring. This coverage can be fully, partially, or not at all. Moreover, this information is complemented with extensions to the current functionalities in order to fulfil the requirements.

Section 5 develops the trustworthiness management system that has been implemented for this iteration. It includes the functional description, the components description, as well as the technical specifications and the delivery and usage.

Section 6 presents a self-assessment model developed for the requirements identified as basic assurance level. This work is complementary to the work that MEDINA is doing for the requirements of assurance level high. The main target users of this work are 1) small and medium CSPs and 2) natural languages processing system that MEDINA is developing for the assessment of organizational measures.

Section 7 concludes this document.

Appendix A: Blockchain Trustworthy management system API description is the Blockchain Trustworthiness management system API description.

Appendix B: Organizational requirements from the draft candidate scheme EUCS version December 2020 presents the EUCS requirements identified as “organizational”.

Appendix C: Self-assessment questionnaires presents the exhaustive checklist.

2 Current state of practice in tools and techniques in management of evidence

2.1 Assessment of security performance configuration of cloud workloads

Cloud environments are fast-changing and can become vulnerable to attacks if not configured correctly. These configuration changes may be hard to detect and include manual configuration changes as well as configuration changes based on upgrades. According to a study [4] about the top threats to cloud computing by the Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) from 2020, two of the top threats to cloud services are misconfiguration and inadequate change control (Top 2) as well as insecure interfaces and APIs (Top 7).

Cloud configuration checking tools can be used to detect these misconfigurations. According to a further study of the CSA from 2021 regarding the state of cloud security both Cloud Provider tools and third-party tools for configuration checking are used about equally often [5]. Furthermore, the study also states that the dominant public cloud platforms in the market are Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud Platform.

Various approaches, architectures, and implementation for cloud security monitoring have been proposed in the last decade. For example, GMonE [6] was one of the first general-purpose cloud monitoring systems. A more recent approach has been proposed by Torkura et al. [7]. They combine cloud monitoring with state transition analysis to build a continuous threat assessment tool for multi-cloud systems. Similar to Cloudfitor [8], this tool, called CSBAuditor [9], uses Cloud APIs to discover existing resources. The results are then compared to the resources' expected states, i.e., via state transition analysis. It also further analyses the results using a dedicated risk analysis component. In comparison to Cloudfitor, however, it does not implement an ontology-based discovery. While this approach is a compact concept and implementation of a multi-cloud auditing tool, MEDINA rather aims at building a modular framework that automates parts of the certification process, e.g., of the EUCS. Since CSBAuditor implements some of the features that are needed in the MEDINA framework, e.g., cloud resource discovery, it could in parts be adapted to fit the MEDINA design requirements (e.g., APIs).

2.1.1 Azure Security Center and Azure Policies

The cloud computing service of Microsoft Azure provides the *Azure Security Center*¹ allowing to monitor various resources deployed within the cloud. One way to improve the monitoring is to use *Azure Policy*² which is a service that lets users create policies. Using these policies helps to comply with the imposed regulations of the company. They can be used to deny the deployment of resources beforehand or give alerts (e.g., in the *Azure Security Center*) about the current state of the deployed resources. There is the option to use pre-built policies or to produce customized policies depending on the specific needs of the respective user.

Although the *Security Center* accompanied with *Azure Policies* provides a good and visualized presentation of the current state of the cloud environment, there are two downsides using this approach. First, the capabilities to monitor resources depend on the expressiveness and scope of the *Azure Policy* language. The main limitation of using Azure's monitoring services, however,

¹ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/security-center/security-center-introduction>

² <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/governance/policy/overview>

is to be tied to Azure. A multi-cloud monitoring approach is not possible using Azure's service exclusively.

By exploiting the respective CSP APIs, the *Cloudfitor* tool has the maximum potential to access information about cloud resources and the ability to monitor multiple cloud services simultaneously – based on the ontology used in MEDINA.

2.1.2 AWS Config, Security Hub

Similar to Azure, Amazon Web Services (AWS) provides its own services for monitoring AWS resources as well. Two options for checking the state of deployed resources are *AWS Config*³ and the *AWS Security Hub*⁴. The same limitations as for *Azure* arise here: being tied to expressiveness of these services and limited to resources of AWS. In addition, the service *AWS Config* cannot be used for free.

As accessing the CSP via its offered APIs is free of charge and the *Cloudfitor* tool is offered as an open-source tool under the Apache 2.0 license, *Cloudfitor* can be freely used, modified and distributed under the terms of the license. In addition, the advantages of using *Cloudfitor* for *Azure* applies.

2.1.3 Commercial tools

There are also commercial tools for monitoring the configurations of one or more cloud computing services. One example is Prisma Cloud [10], a multi-cloud solution for continuous monitoring of cloud configurations. However, such tools are mostly costly and not open source. Since they are not open source, they lack flexibility in use and therefore cannot be easily integrated into a framework like MEDINA.

2.1.4 IaC template export

Another way to discover resource configurations is to exploit the APIs for exporting the IaC (Infrastructure-as-Code) template. It allows to retrieve templates for resources deployed in the cloud service. Such a template provides a comprehensive view about the configuration of the respective cloud resource. In addition to the more holistic discovering provided with the general APIs of the respective cloud service providers, we foresee to implement the discovery via these IaC APIs as well, to obtain a quick overview of the cloud resources' configuration. The export is possible in both Azure and AWS.

2.2 Security assessment of computing infrastructure

This section describes the state of the art of tools used for assessing the security of infrastructural elements such as (virtual) machines and networks. Two types of tools are presented: tools for proactively detecting vulnerabilities (vulnerability assessment) and tools for reactively detecting breaches (intrusion detection). In the scope of MEDINA, these tools are used to obtain evidence about fulfilment of specific requirements by monitoring the state of infrastructure's security, or offered to be used by CSPs to satisfy certain requirements and communicate the fulfilment of these requirements to MEDINA.

2.2.1 Vulnerability assessment

Vulnerability assessment comprises identifying, quantifying, and ranking potential vulnerabilities in computer systems, networks, and applications, and is a critical component of

³ <https://aws.amazon.com/es/config/>

⁴ https://aws.amazon.com/security-hub/?nc1=h_ls

vulnerability and risk management in any company. Vulnerability scanners are automated tools that can aid in the process of identifying vulnerabilities, by checking for security weaknesses or abnormalities in the networks, systems, or applications. Based on the scope of their scanning targets, they are classified as network-based, host-based, wireless, application, and database scanners [11], where a single tool with multiple capabilities (e.g. Nmap [12]) can fall into more than one category. Application vulnerability scanners are further divided into two groups depending on their testing method. Dynamic application security testing (DAST) tools test software in its operational state by using the provided interfaces of running programs to insert specially crafted test inputs, intended to verify the correctness of the program's responses and find error patterns that could indicate security vulnerabilities. DAST scanners do not require application's source code or other data about the software internal operation (black-box testing). On the other hand, static application security testing (SAST) scanners analyse the software's source code and do not require the tested application to be in a running state. SAST methods are described further in Section 2.3.

Among the most used DAST tools are web application vulnerability scanners that scan websites for vulnerabilities such as cross-site scripting (XSS), SQL injection, path traversal, and various insecure server configuration errors. Examples of such tools include AppSpider [13], Burp Suite [14], Nessus [15], Qualys [16] (offered as a service), and open-source tools: OpenVAS [17], Arachni [18], OWASP ZAP [19], and w3af [20]. Beside the general web application scanners, other DAST tools focus on specific vulnerabilities: sqlmap [21] (detecting SQL vulnerabilities) and XXSer [22] (cross-site scripting). DAST scanning tools can be used manually in penetration testing or in an automated way, where the results are later examined by an expert. A comprehensive list of DAST scanners is provided by OWASP [23].

Vulnerability Assessment Tools included in MEDINA (described in Section 4.3) combine multiple open-source DAST scanners in a scanning automation framework in order to extend the scope of scanning and enable scheduling of automated scans, alerting, and basic vulnerability management.

2.2.2 Intrusion detection

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) are software applications that can detect and analyse active attacks or threats in the monitored infrastructure. Depending on the scope of monitoring, IDSs can monitor a single machine, its configurations, files, and applications (host-based IDS, HIDS), or analyse traffic on a network to detect anomalous activity or attacks (network-based IDS, NIDS). Based on the detection technique used, IDSs are grouped into signature-based and anomaly-based. Signature-based IDSs use databases of known attack or malware patterns and simply look for matches in files or traffic they monitor. Anomaly-based IDSs on the other hand use models, built by monitoring the normal system operation and identify anomalies based on deviations from the normal operation. These are more sophisticated and normally use machine learning methods to train their models and classify application logs, behavioural features, files, or network streams into either normal or potentially harmful (malicious). Because host-based IDSs rely on detecting anomalous behaviour, they can also detect new types of threats, while signature-based IDSs are typically more accurate at detecting known threats, but are incapable of detecting previously unseen malware or new types of attacks (0-days) due to their different fingerprints (patterns).

Recent research in intrusion detection methods focuses on improving the machine learning methods for anomaly based IDSs. Various system-level data is utilized to profile the normal system behaviour and detect abnormalities using supervised or unsupervised machine-learning approaches [24]. Some techniques in research focus on specific attack classification (e.g., denial-

of-service attacks) [25] while others are devoted to detection of anomalous traffic without classifying the type of attacks [26].

In order to extend the effectiveness of an intrusion detection system, its detection functionality can be combined or integrated with inspectors and actuators. While the detector is capable of detecting anomalies or threats, inspector software enables review of generated alerts by experts, and actuators can (automatically) perform actions to change the system configuration in order to avoid (further) damage by the detected threat. Multi-module solutions that integrate capabilities of sensors, detectors, inspectors, and actuators exist as well, solutions with the widest capabilities are typically Security Information and Event Management systems (SIEMs) [27].

Two examples of popular IDS tools are Snort [28] and Suricata [29], both signature-based network IDSs. Suricata, the more modern of the pair, supports hardware-accelerated high-bandwidth network captures and decoding of application layer data. Zeek [30] (previously known as Bro-IDS) is a network IDS with prevention capabilities that beside pattern-matching also offers some anomaly detection functionalities with the help of its powerful scripting language. Concerning host-based IDSs, one of the most popular open-source tools is OSSEC [31]. It runs on all major operating systems and consists of a server – agent architecture, where agents (lightweight components installed on monitored hosts) deliver information about detected events to the server that manages the agents. Detection capabilities of OSSEC include file integrity monitoring, collection and analysis of application and system logs, rootkit detection, as well as integration with anti-malware software and APIs (e.g., VirusTotal [32]). Wazuh, also used in MEDINA, is another open-source HIDS that is based on OSSEC, but includes additional functionalities, especially regarding possible integrations with other software. Wazuh is integrated with the ELK stack (storing logs and events into an Elasticsearch [33] database and providing a user-facing UI through Kibana [34]), includes a restful API for management, as well as improved detection capabilities with added rulesets. Detection rulesets also include basic evaluation of compliance with some controls of specific regulations or standards like GDPR and PCI DSS. Wazuh can also retrieve certain data about cloud infrastructure through integrations with Amazon AWS and Microsoft Azure clouds.

2.3 Information of data flows in cloud applications

The security and compliance of cloud applications depend on the secure configuration of interfaces for data exchange and processing of information. Thereby, the full software and application stack must be examined. The security of a cloud application depends equally on the security of interactions between components as well as vulnerability free implementations in software. For each granularity, tools are available that support developers and cloud application designers in developing secure applications.

On the highest level, a cloud application consists of a set of services that in its entirety provides the functionality of a cloud application. As a complex system composed of multiple components the secure configuration of each component must be ensured. Tools like Terrascan⁵, Chef InSpec⁶, Snyk⁷ or Anchore⁸ can identify security problems in Infrastructure as Code specifications. These includes misconfigurations or violations against best practices that increase the chance of having vulnerable cloud applications. Part of these checks are based on

⁵ <https://www accurics.com/developers/terrascan/>

⁶ <https://community.chef.io/tools/chef-inspec>

⁷ <https://snyk.io/>

⁸ <https://anchore.com/>

descriptions how a secure configuration should look like. These in turn are mapped in some cases onto policies. As a result, they can validate compliance to standards like HIPAA, PCI DSS, NIST and CIS benchmarks.

A second class of tool can check if used components are up to date and free of vulnerability. This class of tools often provides some form of container or VM scanner. It checks if used programs and libraries in a container/VM contain outdated software or software with vulnerabilities. Tools like these are, for example, Grype⁹, Clair¹⁰ and Trivy¹¹.

Finally, source code of developed software that is deployed as a component of a cloud application must be developed using secure coding practices. Part of these practices is the use of static security application testing tools. These tools are often included in CI/CD pipelines and scan source code for vulnerable software patterns. Well known tools include products from SonarSource like SonarQube¹², Flawfinder¹³, Semgrep¹⁴ or CodeQL¹⁵ by GitHub. They often contain rules that identify when certain software patterns represent vulnerabilities or violate best coding practices. They may also include softer rules from software engineering that try to reduce the complexity of source code and enforce documentation. These tools help developers to identify problems in their code and fix them before the code is deployed as a production application.

Codyze belongs to this last class of tools. It scans code and identifies potential pitfalls in the use of software libraries that cause vulnerabilities. However, where most of the previous tools stop the analysis, Codyze tries to map low-level code properties to high-level security requirements from control frameworks like ENISA EUCS [3]. Thus, Codyze tries to conclude that the presence of some software properties and absence of vulnerability qualifies a software to comply with control frameworks like ENISA EUCS.

⁹ <https://github.com/anchore/grype>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/quay/clair>

¹¹ <https://github.com/aquasecurity/trivy>

¹² <https://www.sonarqube.org/>

¹³ <https://dwheeler.com/flawfinder/>

¹⁴ <https://semgrep.dev/>

¹⁵ <https://codeql.github.com/>

3 Evidence Management Tool Architecture

This section presents the architecture of the Evidence Management Tool, which integrates several tools, namely Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT), Wazuh, Cloudfoghorn, Codyze and the organizational assessment tool, as well as proprietary tools coming from the MEDINA use cases. The section aims to describe the architecture of this component, its data model and its sequence diagrams.

3.1 Structural description

3.1.1 Architecture and data model

The architecture of the MEDINA framework has been proposed in the deliverable D5.1 [1]. It is composed by several building blocks, as is shown in Figure 1. Each building block corresponds to a well differentiated functionality of the proposed architecture.

In the case of the evidence management, more than one of the depicted blocks take part in the whole process. More concretely, the processes involved are: (i) Technical measures collection and assessment (represented in the picture in the block n. 7); (ii) Organizational evidence gathering and processing (block n. 5); and (iii) Orchestration of evidence management and trustworthiness (block n. 6).

Building block five in MEDINA's framework implements both a **repository for the organizational evidence**, as well as for the NLP-based techniques for their processing. This processing **assesses related documentation** of the CSP (e.g., security concepts, operation manuals) for conformance with the certification scheme's requirements.

Complementary to this functionality in MEDINA, is building block seven, which provides the **assessment of technical measures** by integrating a variety of tools (including native CSP functionalities). This building block seven targets the multi-layer assessment of the target-of-certification cloud service i.e., the related IaaS, PaaS and SaaS stack.

All the assessment results, obtained either from the organizational or technical measures gathered, are holistically **processed, stored and tamper-proofed** by the components shown in building block 6. This block shows also the orchestrator, responsible for launching and stopping the rest of components as well as forwarding data it receives.

Figure 1. Building blocks view of the MEDINA framework (source: D5.1 [1])

A more detailed schema of the components and architecture involved in the evidence management tool is depicted in Figure 2. and described in the next paragraphs. All tools relevant in this document are depicted in green.

Figure 2. Architecture of the Evidence Management Tool (source MEDINA’s own contribution)

CONTINUOUS EVIDENCE GATHERING TOOLS

The Continuous Evidence Gathering component **collects evidence** from the CSPs and post them to the Security Assessment component described in D4.1 [35]. There can be evidence of different nature, and are gathered by different tools:

- **Technical Evidence Collection** tools from the CSP infrastructure (e.g., Clouditor or Wazuh).

- **Vulnerability Assessment Tools**, that extract evidence from system logs.
- **Application-Level Evidence Collection** tool: gathers evidence from the static code analysis or specifications of applications (e.g., Codyze).
- **Organizational Evidence Gathering** tool: organizational evidence is automatically collected by examining the Repository of Documents. The processing part transforms this evidence in the form of technical evidence. The tool uses Natural Language Processing (NLP).

ORCHESTRATOR

The Orchestrator is the component responsible for launching and stopping components in the evidence management toolchain, as well as forwarding data to other components. The Orchestrator gets evidence and assessment results from the Security Assessment and stores them.

The Orchestrator posts the (checksum of the) assessment result to the Evidence Trustworthiness Management. The Orchestrator posts also the assessment results to the Continuous Certification Evaluation for evaluating the result.

The main sub-components of the Orchestrator are

- **Databases** for the storage of evidence and assessment results.

EVIDENCE TRUSTWORTHINESS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The Evidence Trustworthiness Management System provides a secure mechanism for MEDINA to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results involved in the auditing process. It is implemented by means of smart contracts backboned by a blockchain network.

The sub-components of the Trustworthiness Management System are:

- The **Blockchain client**, needed by the Orchestrator to interact with the Blockchain.
- The **Blockchain network** with the required Smart Contracts to provide the trustworthy functionality.
- A **Blockchain monitor** listening to events from the Smart Contracts.
- A **Blockchain monitor client** to consume the information in the monitor and provide it graphically to auditors.

Every time a new evidence or assessment result is received, the Orchestrator writes the corresponding trustworthy information in the component. Then, an event with the information is generated by the Evidence Trustworthiness Management System in Blockchain and is received by the Blockchain monitor.

Data Model

The data model of MEDINA framework has been described in the aforementioned architecture deliverable (D5.1 [1]). It describes the different entities that are needed by the components of MEDINA to work, and which are shared among them. As Figure 3 shows, the entities have been categorized into different groups depending on the building block they belong to.

Figure 3. MEDINA framework data model (source: D5.1 [1])

Figure 4 shows a more detailed diagram, extracted from Figure 3, in which only entities that are related to the Evidence Management Tool are represented, showing their attributes and relationships. The colour code is as follows:

- **Green** entities: Correspond to evidence gathering and assessment.
- **Purple** entities: Correspond to evidence trustworthiness or assessment result trustworthiness.
- **Red** entities: Correspond to security assessment rules.

Figure 4. Detail of the Data Model used by the Evidence Management Tool

The elements that appear in the entity-relation diagram above are described next.

Security assessment rule: is the process that applies a specific Metric to assess if the Security Configuration is compliant with a specific Target Value. The Security Assessment Rule compares a Measurement Result with the specific Target Value to obtain a Security Assessment Result. The security assessment rule is instantiated from a template which references the Metric to apply, but not the specific Target Value to use for the assessment of the Security Configuration.

Examples:

- Requirement text: Check that the retention time configured for a cloud-based SQL database is set to 35 days.
- Check that the maximum password age on a cloud-based Linux VM is set to 30 days.

A Security Assessment Rule *obtains a Security Assessment Result*.

Security assessment result: the outcome of a performed Security Assessment Rule.

Examples:

- Compliant
- Non-compliant

A Security Assessment Result is *linked to* one or more **Evidence**.

A Security Assessment Result has a **Trustworthy assessment result** which *represents* it.

Evidence: existence or verity of something. Objective evidence can be obtained through observation, measurement, test, or by other means. Objective evidence for the purpose of audit generally consists of records, statements of fact or other information which are relevant to the audit criteria and verifiable.

Examples:

- Terraform template for VM being assessed.
- Audit logs from S3 bucket.
- Documented security policy and procedures of a CSP.

An Evidence has a linked **Trustworthy evidence** which *represents* it.

Trustworthy evidence: this is the representation of an evidence produced, stored and managed by the Trustworthiness Management System of MEDINA. This component -based on digital signatures and blockchain technology- guarantees that all the information stored is trustable, and even more, that every piece of data can always be traced back to its creator. Basically, this entity consists of a hash of the evidence and includes a timestamp too.

Trustworthy assessment result: this is the representation of an Assessment Result produced, stored and managed by the Trustworthiness Management System of MEDINA. It includes a hash of the Assessment Result and a hash of the (possible) non-compliance comments, along with the timestamp. It stores a list of Evidence that produced the Assessment Result.

A Trustworthy assessment result is *linked to* one or more **Trustworthy evidence**.

3.1.2 Sequence Diagrams

This section describes the components of the Evidence Management tool architecture using sequence diagrams. Figure 5 shows one sequence diagram for the *continuous evidence gathering and collection, security assessment and orchestrator* components.

Figure 5. Sequence diagram of the Evidence Management Tool architecture

3.1.2.1 *Continuous Evidence Gathering and collection*

The *continuous evidence gathering and collection* component is used to collect evidence from CSPs and post them to the security assessment for further processing. The relevant components for the continuous gathering and collection component are as follows:

- Evidence collection tool, e.g., provided by Clouditor or Wazuh
- Security assessment tool, e.g., provided by Clouditor
- Database for the storage of evidence
- Database for the storage of assessment results

In order to collect and store evidence, the tools involved must first be registered. The registration steps can be found in steps 1 and 2 (the numbering corresponds to the diagram in Figure 5). The sequence for the *continuous evidence gathering and collection* is as follows: *orchestrator* -> *security assessment* > *continuous evidence gathering and collection*.

1. The evidence collection tools must be registered in the security assessment tool so that the security assessment can trigger the evidence collection tool.
2. The security assessment tool must be registered in the orchestrator to enable the orchestrator to trigger the appropriate security assessment tool.

Steps 3 and 4 start the evidence collection.

3. The orchestrator triggers the security assessment tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.
4. The security assessment tool triggers the evidence collection tool to start collecting evidence based on the metric IDs.

The actual gathering and collecting evidence takes place in steps 5 and 6.

5. The evidence collection tool starts the monitoring of the CSPs based on the metric IDs.
6. The evidence collection posts all evidence to the security assessment for future processing and storing. Finally, the orchestrator stores the evidence in step 13 to the corresponding *Database for evidence*. If the *evidence collection tool* should stop, the *orchestrator* sends in step 15 a stop statement with the corresponding metric ID which is passed on by the security assessment.

3.1.2.2 *Security assessment*

The *security assessment* assesses the evidence from the *evidence collection tools* and pushes the results to the *orchestrator*. The sequence diagram is shown in Figure 5. The *evidence collection tool* registration in step 1 is already described in Section 3.1.2.1 and the necessary components for the *security assessment* are

- the Evidence collection tools, e.g., Clouditor or Wazuh, and
- the Orchestrator.

Step 3 triggers the *security assessment* and step 4 triggers the evidence collection tool. Both steps are part of the *security assessment*.

3. The orchestrator triggers the security assessment tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.
4. The security assessment tool triggers the evidence collection tool to start collecting evidence based on the metric IDs.

The actual *security assessment* takes place in steps 6-10.

6. The security assessment gets the evidence from the evidence collection tool.
7. The security assessment gets the target values based on the metric ID contained in the evidence.
8. The security assessment starts the assessment by using the evidence and the target value of step 7. The result is stored in the assessment result.
9. The security assessment posts the assessment result to the Orchestrator and in a later step the orchestrator stores the assessment result in the database (step 14).
10. The security assessment posts the evidence to the orchestrator and in a later step the orchestrator stores the evidence in the database (step 13).

If the *security assessment* should stop, the orchestrator sends in step 15 a stop statement with the corresponding metric ID which is passed on by the *security assessment*.

3.1.2.3 Orchestrator

The orchestrator is the central component and responsible for launching and stopping components in WP3 as well as forwarding data to other components. Figure 6 shows the corresponding sequence diagram. The important components for the *orchestrator* are

- the Security Assessment
- the Continuous certification evaluation (WP4)
- the DLT
- the Database for evidence and
- the Database for assessment results

The *security assessment* tools are registered in the orchestrator as shown in step 2, and step 3 shows the triggering of the *security assessment*.

2. The security assessment tool must be registered in the orchestrator to enable the orchestrator to trigger the appropriate security assessment tool.
3. The orchestrator triggers the security assessment tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.

The relevant steps of the orchestrator are steps 9-14 as follows:

9. The orchestrator gets the evidence from the security assessment.
10. The orchestrator gets the assessment result from the security assessment.
11. The orchestrator posts the assessment result to the continuous certification evaluation for evaluating the result.
12. The orchestrator posts the checksum of the assessment result for the DLT. The creation of these checksums will be implemented in a future iteration.
13. The orchestrator stores the evidence in the database for evidence.
14. The orchestrator stores the assessment result in the database for assessment results.

3.1.2.4 Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

The sequence diagram of the MEDINA *Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is shown in Figure 6. The orchestrator will be the only actor to access the system providing the trustworthy information about evidence and assessment results; or checking the previously recorded value in order to check information integrity.

Figure 6. Sequence diagram of the Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

The important components for the *Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* are:

- The Blockchain client, needed by the orchestrator to interact with the Blockchain.
- The Blockchain network with the required Smart Contracts to provide the trustworthy functionality.
- A Blockchain monitor listening to events from the Smart Contracts.
- A Blockchain monitor client to consume the information in the Monitor and provide it graphically to auditors.

The sequence of events for recording new data in the *Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is the following one:

- The orchestrator permanently writes the trustworthy information about evidence or assessment results every time a new evidence or assessment result is received.
- Every time new trustworthy information about evidence or assessment results is written in the Blockchain, an event with the information is generated.
- As the Blockchain Monitor is permanently listening to the events from the Trustworthy Management system in Blockchain, it will receive all the Blockchain events.
- The monitor client will be subscribed to the interesting events in the Monitor to graphically show the important information.

Once some trustworthy data information about evidence and assessment results is recorded in the Evidence Trustworthiness Management System, the validity of a specific information can be also verified following the next sequence of events:

- The orchestrator will check if a specific hash value associated to a specific evidence or assessment result matches the value previously recorded on the *Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.
- The *Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* will automatically provide the true/false answer about the matching.

4 MEDINA Tools available to gather evidence for high requirements

This section briefly presents the tools that aim to close the gap between the current state of practice (see Section 2), the requirements coming from the draft candidate EUCS [3], the MEDINA framework requirements (see D5.1 [1]) and the use cases' needs (see D6.1 [36] and D6.2 [37]).

As a recap, the evidence management tool as explained in Section 3 is composed of Clouditor, Wazuh, the Vulnerability Assessment Tool, the organizational evidence gathering tool, and Codyze. They are all convened into an orchestrator that is integrated in Clouditor.

The technical details of these tools can be found on Deliverable D3.4 [2].

4.1 Clouditor

Clouditor [8] is an open-source cloud assurance tool with the main goal to continuously evaluate if cloud resources are configured in a secure way and if they comply with requirements defined by the ENISA draft candidate scheme EUCS such as data backup and recovery, logging or data transmission security. Clouditor consists of three components and an overview can be found in Figure 7:

- *Discovery component* for gathering evidence from the CSP.
- *Security assessment component* to assess the evidence against metrics and determine the compliance status.
- *Orchestrator component* as a central component for launching components of the evidence management tools and directing data flows between components.

The *discovery component* discovers resource properties from various CSPs (e.g., AWS S3) and maps the collected *raw evidence* to *mapped evidence* according to the format of the ontology defined in D2.3 [38].

The *security assessment component* provides an interface to evidence gathering components (e.g., the Clouditor discovery component). This evidence is assessed against the metrics it gets from the orchestrator. The *raw evidence*, the *mapped evidence*, and the *assessment results* are then sent to the orchestrator. The raw evidence is sent along for detailed inspection by the auditors.

The *orchestrator component* is a central link in the MEDINA framework and responsible for launching the rest of the evidence management tools and directing the data flow between components also across different work packages. The *Orchestrator's* tasks comprise:

- triggering the evidence collection tools, e.g., the *Clouditor's* discovery component, for collecting evidence,
- getting metrics from the *catalogue of controls & security schemes*,
- providing these metrics to the assessment components,
- receiving evidence and assessment results from the *Clouditor* security assessment component,
- storing evidence and assessment results,
- sending assessment results to the *continuous certification evaluation component* in WP4 and
- sending checksums of evidence to the DLT.

The connections to other components are defined and provided through APIs. An interface for all assessment components is provided, which in addition to the assessment results, also sends the accompanying evidence. For the storage of evidence and assessment results in databases, interfaces are provided to an *evidence storage* and *assessment result storage*, respectively.

The Cluditor tool with its components is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.4 [2].

Figure 7. Overview of the Cluditor components (source: MEDINA’s own contribution)

4.2 Codyze

Codyze is a static code analysis tool that focuses on verifying security compliance in source code, i.e., by inferring the correct use of cryptographic libraries. It operates on code property graphs and is able to handle non-compiling or even incomplete code fragments¹⁶. It also aims at helping developers to generate “*insights into coding patterns of java and c language coding automatically*”¹⁷.

Codyze collects and assesses evidence from source code of cloud application. It can be integrated into a CI/CD pipeline to collect evidence automatically and generate security assessments for further processing in environments such as Eclipse, IntelliJ, VSCode, and Visual Studio Code.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-AISEC/codyze>

¹⁷ <https://tracxn.com/d/companies/codyze.io>

Codyze uses a domain-specific language called MARK¹⁸ to specify what properties source code must exhibit to be considered secure. MARK defines rules that Codyze evaluates. The rules are retrieved from the orchestrator. An evaluation result of a rule can be an evidence or an assessment result. The details depend on the specified rule.

Collected raw evidence are transformed to mapped evidence according to the format of the ontology defined in D2.3 [38]. If Codyze can assess evidence based on MARK rules, it generates assessment results. Evidence and assessment results are submitted to the orchestrator for further processing, presentation, and inspection.

The technical implementation details of Codyze can be found on D3.4 [2].

4.3 Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT)

Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT) is a modular vulnerability detection and scanning framework. It is composed of several integrated vulnerability scanner tools and a possibility to easily include custom scripts to monitor the infrastructure either for availability or to detect specific threats. Scanning tasks can be configured to run periodically following a schedule, triggered manually, or integrated into various CI workflows.

VAT can be used by CSPs to satisfy some EUCS requirements or gather evidence for the requirements related to vulnerability detection, use of encrypted communication, detection of new devices on the network, etc.

Vulnerability Assessment Tools installed inside the CSP's infrastructure, construct evidence containing measurements made about the monitored resources and send these evidence objects to the security assessment component for further processing. The schema of closely related components and interactions between them is shown in Figure 8. Interaction with other MEDINA components is implemented with the use of an Evidence collector component that also interacts with Wazuh (described in Section 4.4). The (Wazuh & VAT) Evidence collector periodically queries VAT's APIs to examine its configuration and scan results in order to determine compliance with various metrics and generate the respective evidence.

Internally, VAT consists of several micro-services: a scheduler that periodically triggers scanning tasks, an API server for external communication, a collection of Docker images that contain the vulnerability scanners (w3af [20], OWASP ZAP [19], Nmap [12]) and logic to interact with other VAT components, a database for storing results, and a web-based user interface for the configuration and review of scanning results.

The VAT component is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.4 [2].

¹⁸ <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-AISEC/codyze-mark-eclipse-plugin>

Figure 8. Schema of Wazuh, Vulnerability Assessment Tools, and related components

4.4 Wazuh

Wazuh [39] is an open-source host-based intrusion detection system (HIDS) with multiple modules that support (SIEM-like) security analytics, log data analysis, file integrity monitoring, vulnerability detection, and other defensive security tasks.

In the scope of MEDINA, Wazuh is offered to the CSPs as a security solution that can help to satisfy several EUCS requirements about malware protection, logging, threat analytics, and automatic monitoring (alerting). It can also serve as an integration point for various other solutions that produce log files. If any erroneous or anomalous log entries appear, Wazuh can alert the users according to the configured rules. By using Wazuh at the CSP's side, MEDINA can gather the information about the configuration of its modules which provides evidence for fulfilment of the various certification requirements.

The deployment of Wazuh consists of several Wazuh agents, programs installed on the monitored machines, and a Wazuh server that gathers data from the agents and acts as their orchestrator. The Wazuh server also contains an Elasticsearch database with a modified Kibana user interface for easier analytics. As presented in Figure 8, Wazuh is connected to the MEDINA components through the Evidence collector component, which connects to Wazuh's APIs to examine the configurations and possible alerts detected, and based on this data generates evidence about the fulfilment of respective metrics.

The Wazuh component is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.4 [2].

4.5 Assessment of organizational measures using Natural Language Processing

While the previous tools focus on the so-called technical evidence, that is, those that can be measured, this tool focuses on the automatic extraction of organizational measures, that is, those that often describe policies and procedures, but not only, as described below.

Audits, even those carried out at regular intervals, require many hours of time to find a wide variety of evidence documents. According to the knowledge of MEDINA partners, this is particularly noticeable in the area of organisational requirements. These are various types of evidence documents that have to be found by CSPs. This evidence can consist of screenshots, pictures, log files, configurations or others. Thus, an extensive manual analysis is currently necessary. Because of the wide variety of different problems, there exists almost no automation as far as MEDINA partners know. Moreover, it is difficult to automate the analysis due to the large variety of evidence types.

To fulfil MEDINA's goal of the assessment of organisational measures, the tool proposed in MEDINA will be used to extract evidence based on metrics from certain documents linked to the organisational measures and process them in a pipeline to prepare them for assessment. The assessment of the evidence produced by this activity is either done consecutively in an assessment tool like Clouditor or performed directly by a subsequent subcomponent. The evidence information is to be retrieved from a wide variety of document types. This can be done by separating certain types of documents and then processing them accordingly, for example through natural language processing (NLP) for natural language-based text documents, or through differential analysis, which uses a golden standard, for other documents.

The process needed in order to solve this task can be summed up by the following points:

- Research methods suitable to extract “audit-relevant” information from an evidence document.
- Gather examples of necessary document types for subsets of requirements and linked examples of the information to be retrieved.
- Categorize the examples and define “clusters”, which can be assigned to methods for extraction and assessment.
- Use explorative approach and (visual) analysis to identify possible methods such as NL for each cluster.
- Select methods and determine for which data types/clusters this process is feasible within the project scope.
- Explore prototypes for selected clusters and build demonstrators.

4.5.1 Document types and methods

The process involves a wide variety of document types. Such documents can be images, .xlsx, .docx, .md, .txt or even .pdf files. This makes a standardised methodology for the extraction of evidence correspondingly difficult. Different document forms can also occur within these file formats. For example, a Word document can contain tabular text as well as full text. This makes this task even more complex as this structure and context is lost when only the text is considered. Therefore, in order to find a way to extract the evidence, the files must first be divided into categories that can be handled in different ways. Furthermore, document sections need to be handled separately if the structure varies (e.g., text, table, figure, diagrams...).

A selection of requirements from the EUCS [3] (see Appendix B), marked as organisational within the MEDINA project, can be used as a basis for this task's experiments. For this, it is necessary

to create metrics and map them to these organisational requirements. These metrics can be used to design specific queries to extract the audit-relevant information from evidence documents. Some metrics might need specific input from the CSP to make the query complete, which could allow to transform an organisational measure to a technical, assessable measure.

4.5.1.1 Dataset

Building a dataset to fulfil all requirements of a security scheme is difficult, as every CSP and every service can produce different types of accepted (=compliant) evidence. At the moment of writing this document, this data set is not yet available. Therefore, one of the main first steps of this task is to gather all evidence documents that could be relevant for reaching successfully the compliance status to a security scheme. To get a generic dataset, the documents should reflect the real-world evidence of CSPs. In a joint effort, exemplary documents and the evidence could be provided by Bosch, Fabasoft and Nixu.

4.5.1.2 Natural language text documents

Text-based evidence will often be provided in the form of .docx documents or .pdf documents containing human-readable text. Here, however, it is often difficult to obtain the required information with classical information extraction and is usually connected with manual searching for the corresponding sentence passages, automated, predefined queries and queries with a predefined structure. For this reason, it is necessary to try NLP approaches to solve this problem. One such NLP option is a *question answering* [40] system.

A question-answering system is an intelligent system that can answer questions asked on the basis of a natural language text document. There are question-answering systems for the extraction of word phrases (e.g.: BERT-SQUAD [41] [42]) as well as for the prediction of yes/no questions. This system can be tested on the official BERT-SQUAD site of huggingface [43]. Such a system is built, for example, on top of a neural network like Bert [44]. Bert is a neural network that can understand human-readable documents by pre-training large amounts of data. This network was retrained with questions and answers in order to be able to answer questions from a given document.

A question answering system can be used, for example, to investigate the current approach for monitoring the security of office buildings. For this, we need to query the document containing the information that includes how the floors are currently secured. The result would be a corresponding extracted text phrase from the given document. This extraction includes a certain degree of confidence. If the confidence is high enough, the result can be compared with a list of possible results. If the result is present in the list, the metric is fulfilled.

The disadvantage of such a system is that it always tries to find a corresponding answer to a question. For example, to the question: "Where is the Eiffel Tower located?" it would also try to find the most likely answer. If the following input text is used: "Fabasoft has its headquarters in Linz", the network will probably give Linz as the answer.

As it can be seen from this example, the correctness of a neural network cannot be guaranteed. Also, model answers to yes/no questions might not be accurate enough, so further research has to be considered here to determine whether such systems provide high quality output usable for this task. However, the model provides a confidence level, which can be considered before using the output for assessment. The extracted evidence with the respective confidence is passed on to Clouditor for further processing and assessment. Thus, it can be decided there whether a manual check is necessary, or the confidence is sufficient. In this case, the result of the network can be used to speed up the manual testing process.

4.5.2 Information extraction from log files

Classical information extraction methods can be used to query for information from log files. Depending on the structure of the log file this can be done using regular expressions (RegEx) or XPath queries or extraction from JSON files. As this is straight forward process, we do not intend to use NLP methods for this type of documents.

4.5.3 Difference analysis

One way of checking documents can also be a simple difference comparison. Here, it is necessary that an existing checked and already audited document is available. This checked document can now be compared with a more recent version. If there is no change, or only an irrelevant change, this document does not have to be further approved. Furthermore, the manual review of documents can be facilitated with the help of a difference analysis.

However, in order to be able to carry out such a difference analysis, a distinction must again be made between document types. Furthermore, thresholds have to be researched that determine whether the change is irrelevant and how manual reviews can influence the assessment.

4.5.3.1 Difference analysis on images

A simple approach here would be to compare the image to predefined (e.g., accepted in a previous audit) evidence image. The difference on pixel level can be calculated. If the difference is 0, the second image is identical to the first and does not have to be checked manually.

However, if a change has been made, a manual check must now be carried out. To simplify this check, the difference analysis can be used to display the change more easily. This can be found by subtracting the first image from the second image. The difference can then be presented to the user as additional information or be highlighted in the original images.

The described approaches will be probably too simple, as different ratios, contrast etc. of images are not considered. Hence, further research should be conducted. However, we do not expect to have a large quantity of evidence images (despite some screenshots). Screenshots or other images could be checked in other ways, as the source document will be some form of a text document, or the image can be OCRed (OCR: Optical Character Recognition) and then treated as such.

4.5.3.2 Difference analysis on textual documents

If the text content is identical to a document that has already been checked, the document to be compared is automatically compliant. However, if this is not the case, a sentence-level differential analysis could be performed to facilitate a manual review. This will highlight new sentences.

4.5.3.3 Byte-wise Comparison

To compare two generic files, one can resort to a byte-wise comparison. Before comparing the two files, the header must not be considered, as this information is usually changed when the file is saved. A byte-wise comparison can now be carried out on the remaining data. The difference analysis for manual difference inspection (by human) only makes limited sense, as the difference cannot always be displayed visually in a meaningful way. As this would be a rather low-level approach, we do not expect to provide much to a working prototype, still it is considered here for completeness.

4.5.3.4 *Difference analysis using document features*

For this purpose, it is necessary to extract features from these already audited documents that allow similarity comparisons on the document corpus. In order to compare text, it is necessary that an algorithm can remotely “*understand*” the text. For this, a vectorisation of the text is necessary. Word embeddings or sentence embeddings can be used. Such embeddings can also be generated by neural networks. Semantic similarities are also considered here.

One of the easiest ways to compare images is to use the pixel values as a feature vector. However, it is important to note that the pixels must be contained in the exact same points on the image (resolution, contrast, etc.).

With the extracted features it is now possible to calculate similarity metrics. For example, cosine similarity can be used for this purpose. Cosine Similarity outputs a score between 0 and 1. If the result is 1 both documents are very likely identical. Closer to 0 means that both documents are not very similar.

A limitation can be seen, for example, if a sentence in a bigger original document is changed just slightly. For example: "The floor is alarmed" to "The floor is not alarmed". Semantically, there is a big difference, but the similarity score only changes slightly. To address this problem, one can combine the similarity score with querying.

More information related to this can be found in deliverable D3.4 [2].

4.6 Summary of the coverage of the requirements of the draft candidate scheme EUCS by the MEDINA Evidence Management Tool

The scope of the certification requirements for MEDINA was defined in D2.1 (section 3.1) [45] where we focused on 33 EUCS requirements that were identified in the draft version of the candidate EUCS scheme released in December 2020. These requirements were elected based on the fulfilment of two requisites: i) they are of high assurance level; and ii) they include the wording “automatically monitor” or variations thereof.

Table 1 shows how the MEDINA tools for gathering technical measures explained above, namely Clouditor, Wazuh, VAT and Codyze, cover those 33 requirements identified in D2.1 [45]. The NLP tool for assessment of organizational measures has not been considered in this analysis because, at the time of writing, it is just a theoretical approach that will be implemented, and therefore considered, in the next iterations of the MEDINA Framework.

The structure of the table is as follows:

- Each row corresponds to a EUCS requirement¹⁹.
- Each column represents a component of the MEDINA Evidence Management Tool.
- For each cell the following information is provided:
 - A background colour, which means:
 - **Green**: the tool covers the requirement.
 - **Yellow**: the tool partially covers the requirement.
 - **Red**: the tool does not cover the requirement and may not be designed for the purpose of covering it.
 - Information on how the tool will be extended in order to fully fulfil the requirement. Please note that, as mentioned before, not all the tools are expected to cover all EUCS requirements.

¹⁹ The EUCS used is the candidate draft version of December 2020 [2]

Table 1. Summary of the coverage of the MEDINA Evidence management tools wrt the draft candidate EUCS [3] and planned functionalities (source: MEDINA own contribution)

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Cloudfitor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
Organisation of Information Security	OIS-02.4 The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.	We plan to add metrics that measure the appropriate assignment of responsibilities, e.g. regarding	It may be possible to check if an application uses mechanisms to segregate duties and if assignments are monitored.		
Security Policies and Procedures	ISP-03.7 The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date	Possible checks include checking for recent document modifications; ideally, this requirement should, however, be covered by T3.4			
Human Resources	HR-03.5 The verification of the acknowledgement defined in HR-03.4 shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.				
Human Resources	HR-04.7 The CSP shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.				
Human Resources	HR-05.4 The CSP shall automatically monitor the application of the procedure mentioned in HR-05.2	Under certain assumptions Cloudfitor can be extended with basic checks, e.g. for asset ownership of (non-) existing accounts; ideally, this			

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Cloudfitor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
		requirement should, however, be covered by T3.4			
Human Resources	HR06.7 The CSP shall automatically monitor the confirmation of non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements by internal employees, external service providers and suppliers				
Asset Management	AM01.06 The CSP shall automatically monitor the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date	We plan to add an Infrastructure-as-Code-based resource discovery to monitor existing resources; in a public cloud, however, the cloud provider has to be trusted with the up-to-dateness with the provided information			
Asset Management	AM03.06 The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.				
Asset Management	AM04.04 The verification of the commitment defined in AM-04.1 shall be automatically monitored				
Physical Security	PS02.10 The logging of accesses shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of PS-02.9				

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Cloudfitor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
Operational security	OPS02.3 The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-02.1	While the (de-) provisioning of services can be monitored, it has to be evaluated if this can be mapped to a pre-configured list of SLAs, e.g., regarding uptime.			
Operational security	OPS.05.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-05.1				
Operational security	OPS.05.4 The CSP shall automatically monitor the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities			Although VAT's primary role are vulnerability scans, some malware checks could be done as well	
Operational security	OPS.07.2 The CSP shall make available to its customers a self-service portal for automatically monitoring their data backup to guarantee fulfilment with OPS-07.1				

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Clouditor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
Operational security	OPS-07.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor their data backups to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-07.1				
Operational security	OPS-09.5 When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the CSP shall automatically monitor the transmission to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-09.1	We plan to check for existence of the backup in the target location.			
Operational security	OPS-12.4 Derived data, including log data, shall be taken into consideration in regulatory compliance assessments.				
Operational security	OPS-13.7 The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection is effective on the list of critical assets in fulfilment of OPS-12.1				
Operational security	OPS-18.6 The CSP shall equip with automatic update mechanisms the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC	Automatic update mechanisms are available for some resource types in public cloud systems. For these, dedicated checks will be added to Clouditor.			Specific checks can be implemented in Wazuh Agents to monitor e.g. update mechanism access logs. This is highly CSP-specific.
Operational security	OPS-21.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor the service components under its responsibility for compliance with hardening specifications			Specific checks for individual hardening specifications can be implemented	

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Cloudfitor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
Identity, authentication and access control management	IAM-03.11 The CSP shall automatically monitor the implemented automated mechanisms to guarantee their compliance with IAM-03	We plan to implement Cloudfitor checks that cover respective mechanisms in public cloud services, e.g., block inactive accounts.			
Identity, authentication and access control management	IAM-03.12 The CSP shall automatically monitor the environmental conditions of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to the corresponding user or to authorized persons		We could check if authentication attempts are logged in source code.		Alerting of authorized persons can be implemented if such logging exists.
Communication security	CS-04.5 The CSP shall automatically monitor the control of the network perimeters to guarantee fulfilment of CS-04.1			Some specific checks of perimeter separation could be implemented.	
Change and configuration management	CCM-03.10 The CSP shall automatically monitor the definition and execution of the tests relative to a change, as well as the remediation or mitigation of issues				
Change and configuration management	CCM-04.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor the approvals of changes deployed in the production environment to guarantee fulfilment of CCM-04.1		Codyze can partly cover this requirement, e.g. by checking git commit sign-offs.		
Change and configuration management	CCM-05.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor changes in the production	Cloudfitor will be extended with an infrastructure-as-code-	Codyze may check for changes in the software environment		

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Clouditor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
	environment to guarantee fulfilment of CCM-05.1	based discovery mechanisms that can easily detect changes in a cloud system. An open issue, however, is how this information can be compared to the existing roles concept (see CCM-05.1)	used to develop applications. Changes can be flagged as no longer meeting specified requirements.		
Procurement management	PM-04.7 The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures relating to the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Configuration of system components; • Performance and availability of system components; • Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and • Recovery time (time until completion of error handling). 	This requirement targets an extension of the monitoring of EUCS requirements to third parties. We will evaluate if the development of a dedicated API for third parties can be integrated regarding the required features.			
Procurement management	PM-04.8 The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the Cloud Service Provider for prompt assessment and action	Automatic identification of violations is an inherent feature of the MEDINA framework, while automatic reports are an open task for future iterations. We will evaluate if this can be			

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Clouditor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
		extended to third parties (similar to PM-04.7).			
Incident management	IM-03.4 The CSP shall allow customers to actively approve the solution before automatically approving it after a certain period				
Compliance	CO-03.4 Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions				
Compliance	CO-03.5 The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP's subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action		Codyze checks for certain classes of vulnerabilities and deviations from requirements. These are currently related to usage of cryptographic libraries. The process is automated as part of a CI/CD pipeline.		
Dealing with investigation requests from government agencies	INQ-03.4 The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators to ensure that they correspond to the determined legal basis	This can be partly covered, by logging accesses; a mapping to specific users,			

Category	Security Requirement [3]	Clouditor	Codyze	VAT	Wazuh
		however, cannot be covered by Clouditor.			
Product safety and security	PSS-04.3 An integrity check shall be performed and automatically monitored to detect image manipulations and reported to the CSC at start-up and runtime of virtual machine or container images	In public clouds, images are normally obtained from a cloud vendor-owned marketplace and cannot easily be checked for integrity. For integrity checks of container images, we plan to implement checks for Docker Content Trust.			

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From Table 1 we can conclude that at the time of writing this deliverable the MEDINA Continuous Evidence Management tools **fully cover 10 of the 33 EUCS requirements** identified in D2.1 [45] (i.e., there is at least one tool covering each of these requirements, as shown by the green cells in Table 1):

- OPS.05.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-05.1
- OPS.05.4 The CSP shall automatically monitor the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities
- OPS.07.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor their data backups to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-07.1
- OPS-12.4 Derived data, including log data, shall be taken into consideration in regulatory compliance assessments.
- OPS-13.7 The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection is effective on the list of critical assets in fulfilment of OPS-12.1
- OPS-21.3 The CSP shall automatically monitor the service components under its responsibility for compliance with hardening specifications
- CS-04.5 The CSP shall automatically monitor the control of the network perimeters to guarantee fulfilment of CS-04.1
- CCM-03.10 The CSP shall automatically monitor the definition and execution of the tests relative to a change, as well as the remediation or mitigation of issues
- CO-O3.4 Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions
- CO-O3.5 The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP's subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action

Furthermore, MEDINA Continuous Evidence Management tools **partially cover 16 of the 33 EUCS requirements** identified in D2.1 [45] (i.e., there is at least one tool that partially covers each of these requirements, as shown by the yellow cells in Table 1). This means that, at the time of writing, only 7 requirements are not supported by the MEDINA Continuous Evidence Management tools.

Taking this into consideration and considering that KPI 4.1 is based on providing techniques for the implementation of 100% of the technical measures contributed in KPI 1.1, and KPI 1.1 is based the coverage of at least 70% of the selected requirements, we can conclude that MEDINA Continuous Evidence Management tools already cover around **30.3% (10/33)** and partially cover around **48.5% (16/33)**. That means a total (partial) coverage of KPI 4.1 around **78.8% (26/33)**.

The next iterations of the MEDINA Continuous Evidence Management tools will improve the current partial coverage (yellow cells) to achieve a complete coverage (green cells). The involvement of new methods or techniques could also provide coverage of current uncovered requirements (red cells), such as the development of the Assessment of organizational measures using Natural Language Processing tool (see Section 4.5).

5 Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

5.1 Functional description

Blockchain technology has started to be considered as a suitable technology for trustworthy purposes [46], [47], [48], [49] as it promises a transparent, secure, and affordable solution to audit trails. First, Blockchain eliminates the need of a central authority for maintaining data records as it decentralizes the information in a distributed network. Furthermore, Blockchain guarantees immutability of the recorded information as it is “copied” in a distributed network. Another key aspect is that information recorded in a Blockchain is digitally signed by its creator so the origin can always be traced back.

Although Blockchain integrity, decentralization, and non-repudiation inherent features make it a suitable technology for audit trails, its use is still not widespread, and its usability is not user-friendly. Nowadays, a Blockchain client is needed for interacting with a Blockchain. This is usually a limiting requirement as nowadays it is not common for users to have a Blockchain client deployed in their systems. That is why a graphical and web-based tool to access the information recorded in the Blockchain in a user-friendly way is highly recommended, making Blockchain totally transparent for external users (for example, auditors) and providing a graphical mechanism to verify the information records in the Blockchain about evidence and assessment results provided by the orchestrators. This way, anyone with permission (authentication is needed), could check the information recorded in the Blockchain without any kind of Blockchain client (Blockchain will be totally transparent).

The MEDINA Blockchain based Evidence Trustworthiness Management System, provides a secure mechanism for MEDINA to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results. In MEDINA, the Trustworthiness management system is implemented in **Smart Contracts** backboneed by a common **Blockchain network** for all the MEDINA framework instances, providing the following **functionalities**:

- It includes the logic for all the orchestrators instances in MEDINA to **provide the required information to be audited** (about evidence and assessment results).
- It provides **long-term information recording**, thanks to the Blockchain inherent benefits (integrity, decentralization, authenticity...).
- It includes the logic for external users to **access MEDINA audited information** (about evidence and assessment results) **in a graphical and user-friendly way**.

Although **security is highly increased through the Blockchain technology**, it also adds some limitations that should be considered:

- The system performance mainly depends on the Blockchain network performance (this could be highly limited for public Blockchains) [50].
- Although Blockchain is considered a secure technology by design, there are still some attacks that, although unlikely, could break its security [51].
- A Blockchain client is needed for providing information to the Blockchain. Although, a docker image has been created for easy deployment, there are still some requirements to be met (see section 5.5), limiting the potential clients.

5.2 Fitting into overall MEDINA Architecture

The Blockchain Based Evidence Trustworthiness Management System, fits the overall MEDINA architecture as shown in Figure 9, providing a common service of trustworthy records to be able to carry out automated inspections if needed guaranteeing information integrity.

Figure 9. Overall MEDINA Architecture (source: D5.1 [1])

On the one hand, considering the MEDINA components, only the **orchestrator(s)** will provide information related to evidence and assessment results. On the other hand, **compliance manager auditors** will be able to consume information recorded on the Blockchain by means of the Trustworthiness management system web-based interface.

5.3 Prototype architecture

Figure 10 shows the MEDINA Blockchain based Trustworthiness management system architecture.

Figure 10. Blockchain based Trustworthiness management system (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

This architecture is composed of five main elements:

- **Blockchain network.** For the first iteration, a Blockchain network with three nodes deployed in TECNALIA servers has been considered. The Blockchain network is going to be offered as a service by TECNALIA to validate the system solution; however, in real deployments, additional nodes from different companies will be recommended for improving the Blockchain network governance. Every information provided by the MEDINA orchestrators to the trustworthy system will be recorded in all the Blockchain nodes in the Blockchain network; by this way, integrity of the recorded information is guaranteed.
- **Smart Contracts.** The Trustworthiness management system functionalities have been implemented in Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network (previous element). Smart Contracts are programs typically used to automate the execution of certain actions, guaranteeing that all actors can be immediately certain of the outcome. Like the information, the Smart Contracts definition is also recorded in all the Blockchain nodes ensuring integrity and secure execution. The Trustworthiness management system functionalities include the registration of data in the Blockchain (evidence and assessment results) to be verified, as well as the use of this previously registered data for integrity verification. In addition, Blockchain based events are also generated for feeding the Blockchain viewer.

- **Blockchain client.** Every orchestrator that uses the functionalities of the Blockchain based Trustworthiness management system needs a Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain (wallet management functionalities, transactions generation, etc.). To make integration and deployment easier, this Blockchain client will be deployed in all the orchestrator instances as a Docker image which exposes an API REST to interact with it.
- **Blockchain viewer.** It listens to the Blockchain events from the Smart Contracts and normalizes and categorizes the details for proper consuming from the Blockchain viewer client. The Blockchain viewer allows to isolate external users from the need of having a Blockchain client to consume information recorded on the Blockchain.
- **Blockchain viewer client:** This is a client consuming the normalized and categorized information from the Blockchain viewer.

5.4 Component description

5.4.1 Blockchain network

The Blockchain network considered for the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system is **Quorum** [52] . This selection is based on the comparative study carried out inside WP4, where different Blockchain technologies have been analysed, concluding that Quorum is the most suitable one (for more details, please refer to D4.1 [35]).

The Quorum Blockchain network has been deployed in TECNALIA for prototype purpose and three Quorum Blockchain nodes form the testing Blockchain network. However, as it has been mentioned before, in real deployments, more nodes from different organizations are needed to improve decentralization and governance of the Blockchain network. These additional nodes need to be permissioned to be part of the Blockchain network, maintaining the network state, running Smart Contracts, and verifying transactions. Figure 11 shows the architecture of each Quorum node.

Figure 11. Quorum Blockchain node architecture (source: MEDINA’s own contribution)

Quorum [52] is a private Blockchain network created by JP Morgan as a fork of the public Ethereum. It stands out for its high maturity level (being a fork of Ethereum means a widely proven background) which reuses existing technology and maintains sync with upcoming versions of Ethereum. Its main advantages are:

- **Advanced Smart Contracts.** In Quorum, Smart Contracts are based on Solidity language, allowing all the logic of a complete “Turing machine”.

- **No cryptocurrency.** The MEDINA Trustworthiness management system does not require any cryptocurrency. For this reason, it is not necessary to complicate the operation of the Blockchain network. In this sense, Quorum stands out because of its high simplicity.
- **Voting based consensus.** Quorum leverages a faster voting-based consensus algorithm [53] which does not require large processing features in the Blockchain nodes. This consensus algorithm is lighter.
- **Private network.** Quorum only allows permissioned nodes to participate; it is a private network.
- **High scalability level.** Quorum is scalable in terms of participants and activities.

The Quorum nodes communicate with Blockchain clients and other Blockchain nodes using the Constellation peer-to-peer system based on secure messages [54]. This module is formed of two components:

- **Transaction Manager:** It communicates the different Quorum nodes by orchestrating private transactions (sending/receiving encrypted payloads among them). It uses the Enclave for cryptographic operations.
- **Enclave:** It executes encryption and decryption operations.

Every information provided by the MEDINA orchestrators to the Trustworthiness management system (evidence and assessment results) and the Smart Contracts with the specific Evidence Trustworthiness Management System functionality will be recorded in all the Quorum nodes.

5.4.2 Smart Contracts

The Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network include all the intelligence (functionalities) for the Trustworthiness management system. The main functionalities are:

User management

There are two kinds of users:

- **Administrators.** These actors are those who can authorize or de-authorize orchestrators to access the Trustworthiness management system. Administrators can also define new administrators or remove existing ones. The default administrator in the system for prototype purposes is TECNALIA.
- **Authorized orchestrators' owners.** These users shall have been authorized by an existing administrator to use the Trustworthiness management system (for example, XLAB, FHG, etc.). Each of these users will own "one" MEDINA orchestrator which can be then registered in the system (there will be just one orchestrator associated to each authorized orchestrator owner because of existing access control policies in the Smart Contract implementation). The information associated to each orchestrator can only be retrieved by its owner. By this way, although the Blockchain network will be common for several authorized owners (information associated to different orchestrators will be recorded in the same Blockchain network), each authorized orchestrator owner will only have access to the information associated to its own registered orchestrator.

Blockchain addresses are used in the Blockchain based Trustworthiness management system for users' identity purposes (the Blockchain address will be the user identifier).

Administrators' functionalities

Administrators can obtain general information about the current status of the Trustworthiness management system (only administrators can execute the following set of functionalities):

- Register a new administrator (the new administrator id is needed).
- Remove an existing administrator (the administrator id is needed).
- Check if a specific user id is an administrator (the administrator id is needed).
- Get the number of administrators in the system.
- Authorize a new orchestrator owner (the new orchestrator owner id is needed).
- De-authorize an existing orchestrator owner (the orchestrator owner id is needed).
- Check if a specific orchestrator owner id is an authorized orchestrator owner (the orchestrator owner id is needed).
- Get the total number of authorized orchestrator owners in the system.
- Get the total number of registered orchestrators in the system.
- Get all the registered orchestrators ids in the system (administrators can only see the registered orchestrator id, but not the information provided during the registering process by the authorized orchestrator owner).

Authorized orchestrator owners' functionalities

Authorized orchestrator owners can register orchestrators. This registration process considers the following data model for each orchestrator identification:

- **id:** It is the internal id used to identify the orchestrator inside the Blockchain Trustworthiness management system. It is automatically generated by the Smart Contract considering its Blockchain address (this is unique).
- **owner:** It refers to the authorized orchestrator owner id who has registered the orchestrator. As in the previous case, it refers to the authorized orchestrator owner Blockchain address as it is considered the user identifier. It is automatically provided by the Smart Contract.
- **timestamp:** It refers to the timestamp in seconds since the epoch of the orchestrator registering process. It is automatically generated by the Smart Contract.

The functionalities related to the orchestrators' owners are:

- Register a new orchestrator (only one orchestrator per authorized orchestrator owner).
- Get the registered orchestrator id.
- Get the associated authorized orchestrator owner id.
- Get the registered orchestrator registration timestamp.
- Add new evidence information (details following the trustworthy evidence data model shown in Figure 12 are needed).
- Get a specific evidence information (the specific evidence id is needed).
- Get all the added evidence ids associated to this orchestrator.
- Add new assessment result information (details following the trustworthy assessment result data model shown in Figure 12 are needed).
- Get a specific assessment result information (the specific assessment result id is needed).
- Get all the added assessment result ids associated to this orchestrator.
- Check the validity of the hash for specific evidence (the specific evidence id and the evidence hash are needed).
- Check the validity of the hash for a specific assessment result (the specific assessment result id and the assessment result hash are needed).
- Check the validity of the hash for a specific assessment compliance result (the specific assessment result id and the assessment compliance result hash are needed).

```
address id;
address owner;
uint256 creationTimestamp;

uint256[] evidencesIds;
struct Evid {
    uint256 id;
    bytes32 valueHash;
    uint256 toolId;
    uint256 resourceId;
    uint256 cspId;
    uint256 timestamp;
}
mapping(uint256 => Evid) public evid;

uint256[] assessmentsIds;
struct Assess {
    uint256 id;
    bytes32 securityAssessmentHash;
    bytes32 complianceHash;
    uint256[] associatedEvidencesId;
    uint256 metricId;
    uint256 timestamp;
}
mapping(uint256 => Assess) public assess;
```

Figure 12. Evidence Trustworthiness Management System data model

Events generation

Every time an operation is executed in the Smart Contract, a Blockchain based event is generated for feeding the Blockchain monitor. The Blockchain based events to be generated include (but are not limited to):

- A new administrator is registered.
- An existing administrator is removed.
- A new orchestrator owner is authorized to use the system.
- An existing orchestrator owner is de-authorized to use the system.
- A new orchestrator is registered by its orchestrator owner.
- New evidence information is provided.
- New assessment result information is provided.

5.4.3 Blockchain client

The orchestrators need the Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain network in general, and with the Evidence Trustworthiness management system functionalities implemented by means of Smart Contracts, in particular. For this purpose, the main functionalities of the Blockchain client are:

Blockchain account management

Every authorized orchestrator owner interacting with the Blockchain based Trustworthiness management system requires a Blockchain account. The account is formed by a Blockchain address, which clearly identifies the user inside the Blockchain network (in fact, it will be considered as the orchestrator owner id in the system because it is unique), and an associated private key, only known by the orchestrator owner (it should be securely kept). The Blockchain

account is usually managed by means of a “wallet” included as part of the Blockchain client implemented in MEDINA in order to make users interaction with the Blockchain network easier (and transparent of any Blockchain dependency).

In this context, the functionalities available in the Blockchain client related to the Blockchain accounts are:

- Create a new Blockchain account. A new address and its associated private key are automatically generated.
- Get the address associated to a specific private key (for validation purposes).
- Add a specific Blockchain account to the Blockchain client wallet (the private key is needed). Only one account can be added to the wallet in MEDINA (this is a limitation defined for MEDINA).
- Get the Blockchain address added to the wallet (for validation purposes). The Blockchain address previously added to the system Blockchain wallet is obtained.

Blockchain transactions creation

Orchestrators need to generate Blockchain transactions to be sent to the Blockchain and be understood by the Smart Contracts deployed on it. The Blockchain client automatically creates the required Blockchain transaction for executing (calling) all the functionalities available in the Trustworthiness management system Smart Contracts. For this purpose, the Blockchain client internally uses the Web3.js library ²⁰.

API REST for external interaction

The Blockchain component exposes an API REST in order to allow the MEDINA orchestrators to easily interact with the Blockchain client for the functionalities previously described. Figure 13 shows the POSTMAN collection prepared for the validation of the trustworthy management system easier. For more details on the API, please refer to Appendix A: Blockchain Trustworthy management system API description.

²⁰ <https://web3js.readthedocs.io/en/v1.5.2/>

Figure 13. POSTMAN collection for validating Blockchain client API

5.4.4 Blockchain viewer

The Blockchain viewer listens to Blockchain based events generated by the Smart Contracts, notifying about new administrators and orchestrator owners in the system, as well as new evidence or assessment results recorded in the Trustworthiness management system. It provides a mechanism for external users (for example, external auditors, external security engineers, etc.) to verify the evidence/assessment results recorded in the Blockchain. Figure 14 shows the internal architecture of the Blockchain viewer.

Figure 14. Blockchain viewer architecture (source: MEDINA’s own contribution)

The Blockchain viewer is composed of four main elements:

- **Eventuem** [55]. It is the component which bridges the Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network with the Trustworthiness management system functionality and the Blockchain Viewer. As it has been explained before, the Smart Contracts automatically generates Blockchain events that will be listened by Eventuem. Eventuem will then use Kafka for transmitting them to Logstash. For listening to the events, it is necessary to be subscribed to events from the specific Smart Contract addresses (every Smart Contract has a Blockchain address, which identifies itself in the Blockchain). In addition, the

specific events format must be also indicated to Eventum (event id, event parameters order, event parameters type).

- **Apache Kafka** [56]. It is the intermediate platform used to distribute Blockchain events between Eventum and Logstash. Kafka uses message queues to provide an asynchronous communications way; this means that the sender (Eventum) and the receiver (Logstash) of the message do not need to interact with the message queue at the same time.
- **Logstash** [57]. It is a log management tool used in the Blockchain viewer for collecting all the events received from Eventum using Kafka queues, and normalising them in a common format before routing them again to Elasticsearch to be processed.
- **Elasticsearch** [33]. It is a distributed search and analysis engine, which allows to store, index and process information. It receives Blockchain events data from the Logstash service and categorize it in four different categories: users, orchestrators, evidence and assessment results. The information stored in Elasticsearch can be recreated from scratch at any time in case of a security incident resulting in a fully reliable source of information. Elasticsearch exposes an API REST for accessing the information.

5.4.5 Blockchain viewer client

There could be several options to consume data from the Blockchain viewer. However, **Kibana** [34] has been considered the best option due to its high compatibility with Elasticsearch as well as the large number of graphical capabilities that it offers, which would highly improve the usability of the system.

Kibana is a graphical interface which displays the information from Elasticsearch in real time and through customised dashboards. As a result, Kibana graphically shows the information from the Blockchain events as shown in Figure 15. The graphical interface is a preliminary version which will be improved in future iterations.

Authentication is required for accessing Kibana dashboards; in addition, different roles can be created for accessing different kind of information in the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system.

5.5 Technical specifications

The main technical specifications about MEDINA Trustworthiness management system are gathered in Table 2.

Table 2. Trustworthiness management system technical specification (source: MEDINA’s own contribution)

DEVELOPMENT	
Type	Software
Operating Systems	Windows or Linux
Databases	Blockchain (Quorum) and MongoDB
GUI	Through Kibana
Programming language	Go, Solidity, JavaScript, Scripting
Development Environment	Solidity, Elastic Stack
INSTALLATION AND DEPLOYMENT	
Software Requirements	Docker engine and its supporting packages
Hardware Requirements	Hardware virtualization support
Containerization	Docker
Communications	Secure HTTP (HTTPS)
EXECUTION	
Execution Time	It depends on the network stability.
Execution Frequency	Asynchronous

5.6 Delivery and usage

5.6.1 Package information

This section is currently not applicable. All the components of the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system are currently provided as a service from TECNALIA. Once the integration with the different orchestrator instances takes place, the Blockchain client will be deployed as a Docker image. *This information will be updated in the next version of this deliverable.*

5.6.2 Installation instructions

This section is currently not applicable. All the components of the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system are currently provided as a service from TECNALIA and no installation is needed at this phase. Once the integration with the different orchestrator instances takes place, the Blockchain client will be deployed as a docker image. *This information will be updated in the next version of this deliverable.*

5.6.3 User Manual

The current implementation of the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system is completely deployed on TECNALIA premises as a first implementation; once the integration phase takes place, the Blockchain client will be deployed in different orchestrators’ systems. In this first prototype, the interaction is just with a “testing” Blockchain client which exposes an API REST.

The correct sequence of steps for testing and validating all the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system functionalities is:

1. A Blockchain account needs to be generated and added to the Blockchain wallet (inside the Blockchain client).
2. The “testing” Blockchain client (in TECNALIA premises) simulates a Blockchain client hypothetically in an orchestrator system to provide evidence and assessment results information. For this reason, administrator permissions are first needed (in practice, TECNALIA will give the permissions to the orchestrator owners, but for testing purposes in this first implementation, the possibility of providing administrator self-given permissions is also included). Once the “testing” Blockchain client has administrator permissions, it will be able to execute (and validate) all the Administrators functionalities from the Trustworthiness Management system. Refer to Appendix A: Blockchain Trustworthy management system API description to see the available functionalities.
3. Then, we should authorize ourselves as a hypothetical authorized orchestrator owner to be able to use the Trustworthiness management system data functionalities (as in step 2, in practice TECNALIA will give the permissions to the orchestrator owners, but for testing purposes, but for testing purposes in this first implementation, the possibility of providing authorized orchestrator owner self-given permissions is also included). Once the “testing” Blockchain client is an authorized orchestrator owner, it will be able to execute (and validate) all the Authorized orchestrator owners’ functionalities from the Trustworthiness Management system, taking into account that just one orchestrator can be registered per orchestrator owner. Refer to Appendix A: Blockchain Trustworthy management system API description to see the available functionalities.

In addition, the correct sequence of steps for testing and validating all the functionalities from the web-based Blockchain viewer client (Kibana) is:

1. Login in the system is required (only authenticated users can access the dashboard).
2. Go to “Dashboard” section (under Analytics section) by pressing the “three-lines” button in the left. Then, select MEDINA dashboard.
3. The MEDINA dashboard appears. The current status of the information recorded on the Blockchain from the MEDINA Trustworthiness management system about users, authorized orchestrators, evidence, and assessment results can be checked.

5.6.4 Licensing information

Proprietary. Copyright by TECNALIA.

5.6.5 Download

This section is currently not applicable. All the components of the Trustworthiness management system are provided as a service from TECNALIA and TECNALIA will own a proprietary license, so no source code will be provided.

6 Checklist for basic assurance level security requirements

In response to Article 54 recital (g) of the EUCSA [58] which states that “A European cybersecurity certification scheme shall include at least the following elements [...] (g) the specific evaluation criteria and methods to be used, including types of evaluation, in order to demonstrate that the security objectives referred to in Article 51 are achieved;” EUCS [3] has defined an evidence-based assessment approach that is to be used solely for the basic level of assurance.

The proposed evidence-based conformity assessment approach states that the evaluation does not require a “full-fledged audit of the cloud service to be certified” [3] but it is more oriented towards “facilitating a controlled environment for providing limited assurance while keeping the associated cost for certification affordable for smaller CSP’s” [3] and follows a checklist-oriented approach.

The process to be followed is similar to the one a CSP would need to follow in order to get certified, in which it would need to create the application request, define the scope of certification, create the audit plan, execute the assessment procedures, analyse the results, issue the assurance report, review the evaluation, and obtain the certification.

The difference here is that in the basic level of assurance, the CSP itself, and not an external or third-party auditor, creates and carries out the audit plan and executes the assessment procedures, also analysing the results, who are sent to the CAB for further analysis and audits. A simplified version of the process is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Evidence-based conformity assessment (adapted from [3])

Hence, the challenge here is: how to guide CSPs, especially smaller ones in this evidence-based conformity assessment methodology, since this checklist is not yet available or how it can be complemented? (e.g., do not show example of evidence that can be delivered and can be considered valid to demonstrate the compliance of a requirement).

The goal of this checklist is therefore to develop an assessment model for requirements in the basic level of assurance that can be understood by less experienced compliance managers and CSPs in general. However, CABs and auditors could also use it as guidance.

The questions are extracted directly from the requirements themselves. They have been split for understandability reasons into multiple questions, that is, from one requirement multiple questions have been created. However, the number of overall questions is important as this self-assessment model cannot be very heavy and difficult to use. The current number of questions is shown in the next table:

Number of requirements of Basic assurance level in EUCS (version December 2020) [3]	Number of questions elicited in the self-assessment questionnaires
220	532

It is based on the experience of the auditors and consultants that have worked in the checklist, with feedback incorporated from the CSPs that participated in MEDINA, as well as from literature. The number of questions as well as the formulation may evolve as soon as the validation starts.

In addition to the questions, a very important aspect that needs to be considered in the checklist is the evidence. ISO 9000 defines evidence as the data supporting the existence or verity of something [59]. In MEDINA, two types of evidence are distinguished:

- **Technical evidence:** data that supports the compliance of a technical requirement or measure. Examples: protocol version, password length.
- **Organizational evidence:** data that supports the compliance of an organizational requirement. Example: existence of a policy and procedure document.

Hence, the checklist identifies some examples of evidence that the CSP shall submit to the CAB for the evaluation assessment. The evidence examples shown are not meant to be an exhaustive list but just a guidance.

The checklist with the questions is presented in Appendix C: Self-assessment questionnaires, under a tabular form with the following structure:

- **ReqID:** id of the requirement coming from the draft candidate scheme EUCS, version December 2020 [3]. As mentioned before, for this self-assessment questionnaire the focus is on the requirements identified as basic assurance level.
- **Requirement:** description of the requirement coming from the draft candidate scheme EUCS, version December 2020 [3]. As mentioned before, for this self-assessment questionnaire the focus is on the requirements identified as basic assurance level.
- **Question ID:** unique identified of each question, related to each requirement.
- **Statement / Question:** question that the CSP should answer in the evaluation to comply with the requirement as requested in the scheme.
- **Evidence:** the document, section of a document, or any kind of information that the CSP is required to provide in order to prove that the requirement is properly implemented in accordance with what it is required. The list provided is not meant to be exhaustive but rather an indication of what kind of information is expected to be provided.

The main target users of this checklist are small CSPs. However, auditors and CABs could also benefit from it.

7 Conclusions

This document has presented the architecture of the MEDINA evidence management tool [KR4], which comprises the integration of Clouditor, Codyze, Wazuh and Vulnerability Assessment tool and the evidence trustworthiness management system that aims at ensuring that all evidence and assessment results are secured. This is done by means of smart contracts.

The deliverable has started by introducing the state of practice in the domains that the MEDINA evidence management tools cover, namely in the field of security performance configuration of cloud workloads, security assessment of computing infrastructure, and more specifically in regard to vulnerability assessment and intrusion detection, and finally in regard to the information dataflows in cloud applications.

The architecture, data model and sequence diagrams are also detailed, extending the models and explanations already presented in D5.1 [1].

The document then deepens into the main ideas and motivation for the further development of the tools that comprise the MEDINA evidence management tool, even if the technical details of the implementation are provided in D3.4 [2]. As a next step, and in order to plan these further developments the coverage of the requirements of assurance level high coming from the draft candidate EUCS scheme version of December 2020 [3] has been matched with the different tools comprising the MEDINA evidence management tool, identifying the main gaps to be covered with the evolution of existing tools or with new techniques.

The functional and technical details of the evidence trustworthiness management system, how it fits into MEDINA, the architecture of the prototype, the description of the prototype and how it is delivered have also been presented. It is based on smart contracts and currently deployed on a blockchain network in TECNALIA. This is a first prototype that will be evolved taking into consideration theoretical analysis from D4.1 [35] related to hashing techniques and automation methods for making its use more friendly to auditors. Additionally, although the functionality of the tool is complete, some security and usability aspects will be improved.

Finally, and even if MEDINA focuses mostly on the automated monitoring and the high assurance level of the EUCS, CSPs may struggle in the basic level, especially smaller ones. The checklist explained in section 6 and presented Appendix C is aimed at these small CSPs so that they are guided in their self – assessment activities and can know which kind of evidences they are to provide to the CABs when doing the third-party assessment.

Future versions of this document will include updated versions of the evidence trustworthy management system with new features, as well as the checklist presented in section 6. A checklist for higher levels of assurance will also be explored. Furthermore, compositional certification and how this can be addressed in the cloud supply chain will also be investigated.

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Appendix A: Blockchain Trustworthy management system API description

In the current prototype (before the integration phase), one Blockchain client has been deployed in TECNALIA servers exposing the API REST in: <https://medina.bclab.dev/client> [internal use only - authentication required]. The available routes are:

Blockchain account Management

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/account> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Create a new Blockchain account
 - Method: POST
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "address": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825",  
  "privateKey": "0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/account?privatekey=0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get address associated to a private key
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: privatekey
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "address": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825",  
  "privateKey": "0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a "  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/wallet?privatekey=0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Add account to wallet
 - Method: POST
 - Parameters: privatekey
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "walletaddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/wallet> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get account added to the wallet
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "walletaddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

Blockchain transactions generation: General system management

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Add a new administrator
- Method: POST
- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "walletaddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Remove an existing administrator
- Method: DEL
- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "walletaddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Check if an id is administrator
- Method: GET
- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "isadmin": "true"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Authorize an owner to use the trustworthy management system
- Method: POST
- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "authorizedowneraddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Deauthorize an owner to use the trustworthy management system
- Method: DEL
- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "authorizedowneraddress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Check if an id is an authorized owner
- Method: GET

- Parameters: address
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "isauthorizedowner": "true"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admins> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get the number of administrators in the system
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "adminnum": "3"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowners> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get the number of authorized owners in the system
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "authorizedownersnum": "4"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestratorsnum> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get the number of orchestrators registered in the system
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "orchestratorsnum": "5"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrators> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Get the orchestrators ids (addresses) registered in the system
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: None
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "orchestratorsaddresses":  
  "0x55456e0Bd0E46Ec4276Eac51cfC281D39e2cD449,0xF2c6cF607dCbF1BF4E885ae6099eC7cF1Cc0ac51,0  
x2B09939744d8c8Be9e23d05C1D04552F203B06D3,0xA3929A5dC7B0DAdB25004443F77bd9C47b56F4A4,0x0  
dE4b77C6683Bd29fAa3fa8FCdCEf1b2F3aef8b"  
}
```

Blockchain transactions generation: Orchestrator functionalities

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Register an orchestrator in the trustworthy management system
 - Method: POST

- Parameters: None
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/id> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Get the orchestrator id (address)
- Method: GET
- Parameters: None
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "id": "0x0dE4b77C6683Bd29fAa3fa8FCDdCEf1b2F3aef8b"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/owner> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Get the orchestrator owner
- Method: GET
- Parameters: None
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "owner": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/creationtime> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Get the orchestrator creation time
- Method: GET
- Parameters: None
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "creationTime": "1633587655151352261"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence?id=1&hash=0x7465737400&tool=1&resource=2&csp=3> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Record a new evidence from the orchestrator
- Method: POST
- Parameters: id, hash, tool, resource and csp.
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "evidenceId": "1",  
  "evidenceHash": "0x7465737400000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",  
  "evidenceTool": "1",  
  "evidenceResource": "2",  
  "evidenceCsp": "3"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence/{id}> [internal use only - authentication required]

- Description: Get the evidence information of the provided evidence id

- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "assessments": "123,456"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence/check> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Check the recorded hash value for a specific evidence id
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: id and hash
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "correctevidencehash": "true"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment/checkhash> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Check the recorded result hash value for a specific assessment id
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: id and result hash
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "correctassessmenthash": "true"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment/checkcompliance> [internal use only - authentication required]
 - Description: Check the recorded compliance hash value for a specific assessment id
 - Method: GET
 - Parameters: id and compliance hash
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "correctcompliancehash": "true"  
}
```

Appendix B: Organizational requirements from the draft candidate scheme EUCS version December 2020

The following table shows the requirements from the draft candidate scheme EUCS version December 2020 [3] identified as organisational.

Requirements that are simultaneously technical and organizational are marked in green.

Table 3. Identified organizational requirements from the draft candidate scheme EUCS version December 2020 (source: MEDINA own contribution)

Category	Security requirement Id	
Organization of Information Security	OIS-01.1	OIS-02.3
	OIS-01.2	OIS-03.1
	OIS-01.3	OIS-03.2
	OIS-01.4	OIS-03.3
	OIS-01.5	OIS-04.1
	OIS-02.1	OIS-04.2
	OIS-02.2	
Information security policies	ISP-01.3	ISP-02.6
	ISP-01.4	ISP-02.7
	ISP-01.5	ISP-03.1
	ISP-02.1	ISP-03.2
	ISP-02.2	ISP-03.3
	ISP-02.3	ISP-03.4
	ISP-02.4	ISP-03.5
	ISP-02.5	ISP-03.6
Risk Management	RM-01.1	RM-03.3
	RM-01.2	RM-03.4
	RM-02.1	RM-03.5
	RM-02.2	RM-03.6
	RM-02.3	RM-03.7
	RM-02.4	RM-03.8
	RM-03.1	
	RM-03.2	
Human Resources	HR-01.1	HR-03.2
	HR-01.2	HR-03.3
	HR-01.3	HR-03.4
	HR-01.4	HR-04.8
	HR-02.1	HR-04.9
	HR-02.2	HR-04.10
	HR-02.3	HR-05.1
	HR-03.1	HR-05.2
HR-03.2	HR-05.3	

Category	Security requirement Id	
	HR-03.3 HR-03.4 HR-01.4 HR-02.1 HR-02.2 HR-02.3 HR-03.1	HR-06.1 HR-06.2 HR-06.3 HR-06.4 HR-06.5 HR-06.6
Asset Management	AM-01.1 AM-01.3 AM-01.4 AM-01.5 AM-02.1 AM-02.2 AM-02.3 AM-03.1 AM-05.4 AM-03.2	AM-03.3 AM-03.4 AM-03.5 AM-03.6 AM-04.1 AM-04.2 AM-04.3 AM-05.1 AM-05.2 AM-05.4
Physical Security	PS-01.1 PS-01.2 PS01-3 PS-01.4 PS-01.5 PS-01.6 PS-01.7 PS-02.1 PS-02.2 PS-02.3 PS-02.4 PS-02.5 PS-02.6 PS-02.7 PS-02.8 PS-02.9 PS-03.1 PS-03.2	PS-03.3 PS-03.4 PS-04.1 PS-04.2 PS-04.3 PS-04.4 PS-04.4 PS-04.5 PS-04.6 PS-04.7 PS-04.8 PS-05.1 PS-05.2 PS-05.3 PS-05.4 PS-05.5 PS-05.6
Operational security	OPS-01.1 OPS-01.2 OPS-01.3 OPS-02.1 OPS-02.2	OPS-13.1 OPS-13.2 OPS-13.4 OPS-13.5 OPS-13.6

Category	Security requirement Id	
	OPS-04.1	OPS-14.1
	OPS-04.2	OPS-14.2
	OPS-04.3	OPS-14.3
	OPS-04.4	OPS-15.2
	OPS-05.1	OPS-16.1
	OPS-05.2	OPS-17.1
	OPS-06.1	OPS-17.2
	OPS-06.2	OPS-17.3
	OPS-07.1	OPS-17.4
	OPS-08.1	OPS-18.1
	OPS-08.2	OPS-18.2
	OPS-08.3	OPS-18.3
	OPS-08.4	OPS-18.4
	OPS-08.5	OPS-18.5
	OPS-09.1	OPS-19.1
	OPS-09.2	OPS-19.2
	OPS-09.3	OPS-19.2
	OPS-09.4	OPS-19.3
	OPS-10.1	OPS-19.4
	OPS-10.2	OPS-19.5
	OPS-11.1	OPS-19.6
	OPS-11.2	OPS-19.7
	OPS-11.3	OPS-20.1
	OPS-11.4	OPS-20.2
	OPS-12.1	OPS-21.1
	OPS-12.2	OPS-21.2
		OPS-22.1
Identity, authentication and access control management	IAM-01.1	IAM-05.1
	IAM-01.2	IAM-05.2
	IAM-01.3	IAM-05.3
	IAM-02.1	IAM-05.4
	IAM-02.2	IAM-05.5
	IAM-02.3	IAM-06.1
	IAM-02.4	IAM-06.3
	IAM-02.5	IAM-06.4
	IAM-02.6	IAM-06.5
	IAM-02.8	IAM-06.6
	IAM-03.1	IAM-07.1
	IAM-03.2	IAM-08.1
	IAM-03.3	IAM-08.2
	IAM-03.4	IAM-08.3

Category	Security requirement Id	
	IAM-03.5 IAM-03.8 IAM-03.9 IAM-04.1 IAM-04.2 IAM-04.4 IAM-04.5 IAM-04.6	IAM-08.7 IAM-08.8 IAM-08.9 IAM-09.2 IAM-09.3 IAM-09.5 IAM-09.6
Cryptography and key management	CKM-01.1 CKM-01.2 CKM-01.3 CKM-02.1 CKM-02.2 CKM-03.1 CKM-03.2	CKM-03.3 CKM-03.4 CKM-04.1 CKM-04.2 CKM-04.3 CKM-04.4
Communication security	CS-01.1 CS-01.2 CS-01.3 CS-01.4 CS-01.5 CS-02.1 CS-03.1 CS-03.2 CS-03.3 CS-03.4 CS-03.5 CS-03.6 CS-03.7 CS-04.1 CS-04.2 CS-04.3	CS-04.4 CS-05.1 CS-05.2 CS-05.3 CS-05.5 CS-06.1 CS-06.2 CS-07.1 CS-07.2 CS-07.3 CS-07.4 CS-08.1 CS-08.2 CS-08.3 CS-09.1 CS-09.2
Portability and interoperability	PI-01.1 PI-01.2 PI-01.1	PI-02.2 PI-02.3 PI-03.4 PI-03.5
Change and configuration management	CCM-01.1 CCM-01.2 CCM-02.1 CCM-02.2 CCM-02.3	CCM-03.4 CCM-03.5 CCM-03.6 CCM-03.8 CCM-03.9

Category	Security requirement Id	
	CCM-02.4 COM-02.5 CCM-03.1 CCM-03.2 CCM-03.3	CCM-04.1 CCM-04.2 CCM-05.1 CCM-06.2
Development of information systems	DEV-06.1 DEV-06.2 DEV-06.3 DEV-06.4 DEV-06.5	DEV-06.6 DEV-07.1 DEV-07.2 DEV-07.3 DEV-07.4
Procurement management	PM-01.1 PM-01.2 PM-01.3 PM-01.4 PM-01.5 PM-02.1 PM-02.2 PM-02.3 PM-02.4 PM-02.5 PM-03.1 PM-03.2	PM-03.3 PM-04.1 PM-04.2 PM-04.3 PM-04.4 PM-04.5 PM-04.6 PM-04.7 PM-04.8 PM-05.1 PM-05.2
Incident management	IM-01.1 IM-01.2 IM-01.3 IM-01.4 IM-01.5 IM-01.6 IM-01.7 IM-01.8 IM-02.1 IM-02.2 IM-02.3 IM-02.4 IM-02.5 IM-03.1 IM-03.2 IM-03.3	IM-03.4 IM-04.1 IM-04.2 IM-04.3 IM-05.1 IM-05.2 IM-06.1 IM-06.2 IM-06.3 IM-06.4 IM-07.1 IM-07.2 IM-07.3 IM-07.4 IM-07.5
Business continuity	BC-01.1 BC-01.2 BC-01.3	BC-03.2 BC-03.3 BC-03.4

Category	Security requirement Id	
	BC-02.1 BC-02.2 BC-02.3 BC-03.1	BC-04.1 BC-04.2 BC-04.3 BC-04.4
Compliance	CO-01.1 CO-01.2 CO-01.3 CO-01.4 CO-02.1 CO-02.2 CO-02.3 CO-03.1	CO-03.2 CO-03.3 CO-03.4 CO-03.5 CO-03.6 CO-03.7 CO-04.1 CO-04.2
User documentation	DOC-01.1 DOC-01.2 DOC-01.3 DOC-01.4 DOC-01.5 DOC-02.1 DOC-02.2 DOC-02.3 DOC-02.4 DOC-02.5 DOC-03.1 DOC-03.2 DOC-03.3 DOC-03.4	DOC-04.1 DOC-04.2 DOC-04.3 DOC-04.4 DOC-05.1 DOC-05.2 DOC-05.3 DOC-05.4 DOC-06.1 DOC-06.2 DOC-06.3
Dealing with investigation requests from government agencies	INQ-01.1 INQ-01.2 INQ-02.1 INQ-03.1	INQ-03.2 INQ-03.3 INQ-03.4
Product safety and security	PSS-01.1 PSS-01.4 PSS-01.5 PSS-02.1 PSS-02.2 PSS-02.3 PSS-03.1	PSS-03.2 PSS-03.3 PSS-04.1 PSS-04.2 PSS-04.3 PSS-05.1 PSS-05.2

Appendix C: Self-assessment questionnaires

Organization of Information Security

Table 4. Checklist for OIS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OIS-01.1B	The CSP shall define, implement, maintain and continually improve an information security management system (ISMS), covering at least the operational units, locations and processes for providing the cloud service	Q1-OIS-01.1B	Has the CSP an information security management system (ISMS) documented?	- Documented Information Security Management System (ISMS)
		Q2-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement an information security management system (ISMS)?	- Quality records derived from the implementation of the defined ISMS
		Q3-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP maintain an information security management system (ISMS)?	- Documented updates and changes to the ISMS
		Q4-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP continually improve the information security management system (ISMS)?	- Documented improvement actions to the ISMS - Documented ISMS improvement plan - Documented improvements to the ISMS
		Q5-OIS-01.1B	Does the information security management system cover the operational units?	- ISMS scope (operational units)
		Q6-OIS-01.1B	Does the information security management system (ISMS), cover locations?	- ISMS scope (locations)
		Q7-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP cover processes for providing the cloud service?	- ISMS scope (processes for providing the cloud service)

ReqID	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OIS-01.2B	The CSP shall document the measures for documenting, implementing, maintaining and continuously improving the ISMS	Q1-OIS-01.2B	Does the CSP document the measures for documenting the ISMS? These measures shall include at least the scope of measures, the security baseline, objectives of the maintenance of the ISMS (e.g. frequency)	- ISMS: Documented measures
		Q2-OIS-01.2B	Does the CSP document the measures for implementing the ISMS? Among other aspects the following aspects shall be included: roles and responsibilities, security objectives, risk register (see next), awareness activities (internal and external), implementation team, monitoring and review process.	- ISMS: Documented measures
		Q3-OIS-01.2B	Does the CSP document the measures for continuously improving the ISMS? This shall include the at least the definition, implementation, collection and assessment of metrics to be able to improve the ISMS	- ISMS: Documented measures
OIS-02.1B	The CSP shall perform a risk assessment as defined in RM-01 about the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks on roles or individuals, regarding the provision of the cloud service, covering at least the following areas, insofar as these are applicable to the provision of the cloud service and are in the area of responsibility of the CSP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations (cf. IAM-01); • Development, testing and release of changes (cf. DEV-01, CCM-01); and • Operation of the system components. 	Q1-OIS-02.1B	Does the CSP perform a risk assessment as defined in RM-01?	- Documented risk assessment

ReqID	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment address the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks in roles or individuals, with respect to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks in roles or individuals, with respect to the provision of the cloud service)
		Q3-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations (cf. IAM-01)?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with the administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations) - Documented risk assessment review record
		Q4-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover development, testing and release of changes (cf. DEV-01, CCM-01)?	- Documented risk assessment (information related to development, testing and release of changes) - Documented risk assessment review record
		Q5-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover the operation of the system components / assets?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with operation of the system components) - Documented risk assessment review record

ReqID	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OIS-02.2B	The CSP shall implement the mitigating measures defined in the risk assessment, privileging separation of duties, unless impossible for organisational or technical reasons, in which case the measures shall include the monitoring of activities in order to detect unauthorised or unintended changes as well as misuse and the subsequent appropriate actions	Q1-OIS-02.2B	Does the CSP implement the mitigating measures defined in the risk assessment?	- Quality records derived from the implementation of the defined Risk Assessment. The records shall include at least the following information: mitigation measure applied, linked requirement id, by whom it was applied, the date, the asset affected.
		Q2-OIS-02.2B	Do the mitigating measures privilege separation of duties, unless impossible for organisational or technical reasons?	- Quality records derived from the implementation of the defined Risk Assessment related with the privilege separation of duties
		Q3-OIS-02.2B	In case of organisational or technical reasons that prevent privileging separation of duties, do the measures include the monitoring of activities in order to detect unauthorised or unintended changes as well as misuse and the subsequent appropriate actions?	- Quality records derived from the implementation of the defined Risk Assessment related with the monitoring of activities in order to detect unauthorised or unintended changes as well as misuse and the subsequent appropriate actions
OIS-03.1B	The CSP shall stay informed about current threats and vulnerabilities	Q1-OIS-03.1B	Do the CSP stay informed about current threats and vulnerabilities?	- CVE - Online Threat Intelligence investigation records - Subscription to other sources
OIS-04.1B	The CSP shall include information security in the project management of all projects that may affect the service, regardless of the nature of the project	Q1-OIS-04.1B	Does the CSP include information security in the project management of all projects that may affect the service, regardless of the nature of the project?	- Project management documentation (information related with the information security)

Information Security Policies

Table 5. Checklist for ISP basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-01.1B	<p>The CSP shall document a global information security policy covering at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the importance of information security, based on the requirements of cloud customers in relation to information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided • the security objectives and the desired security level, based on the business goals and tasks of the Cloud Service Provider; • the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives. • the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives set; and • the organisational structure for information security in the ISMS application area. 	Q1-ISP-01.1B	Is there a document describing the global information security policy?	- Global information security policy document
		Q2-ISP-01.1B	Does the policy cover the importance of information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided?	- Global information security policy document (includes the importance of information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided)

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the security objectives and the desired assurance and security level, based on the business goals of the Cloud Service Provider?	- Global information security policy document (includes the security objectives and the desired security level, based on the business goals and tasks of the Cloud Service Provider)
		Q4-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives?	- Global information security policy document (includes the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives)
		Q5-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives set?	- Global information security policy document (includes the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives set)
		Q6-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the organisational structure for information security in the cloud service application area?	- Global information security policy document (includes the organisational structure for information security in the ISMS application area)

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-01.2B	The CSP's top management shall approve and endorse the global information security policy	Q1-ISP-01.2B	Does the global information security policy or the organizational structure document establish who is the top management responsible for?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global information security policy document (establishes who is the top management responsible for) - Organizational structure
		Q2-ISP-01.2B	Does the top management approve and endorse the global information security policy?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Top management signature of the global information security policy document
ISP-01.3B	The CSP shall communicate and make available the global information security policy to internal and external employees and to cloud service customers	Q1-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all internal employees?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q2-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all external employees ?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web - eMail -Etc.
		Q3-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all cloud service customers?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service contract - Web - eMail -Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-02.1B	<p>The CSP shall derive policies and procedures from the global information security policy for all relevant subject matters, documented according to a uniform structure, including at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives; • Scope; • Roles and responsibilities within the organization; • Roles and dependencies on other organisations (especially cloud customers and subservice organisations); • Steps for the execution of the security strategy; and • Applicable legal and regulatory requirements. 	Q1-ISP-02.1B	Has the CSP identified all the relevant subject matters within the scheme?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific document that includes information about the relevant subject matters within the scheme - Global information security policy - Etc.
		Q2-ISP-02.1B	Does the CSP derive policies and procedures from the global information security policy for all relevant subject matters?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies and procedures for each subject matter
		Q3-ISP-02.1B	<p>Does the CSP document the policies and procedures derived from the global one following a uniform structure, including at least the following aspects?:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives; • Scope; • Roles and responsibilities within the organization; • Roles and dependencies on other organisations (especially cloud customers and subservice organisations); • Steps for the execution of the security strategy; and • Applicable legal and regulatory requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies and procedures template - Policies and procedures for each subject matter

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-02.2B	The CSP shall communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all internal and external employees	Q1-ISP-02.2B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all internal employees?	- Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q2-ISP-02.2B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all external employees?	- Web - eMail -Etc.
ISP-02.3B	The CSP's top management shall approve the security policies and procedures or delegate this responsibility to authorized bodies	Q1-ISP-02.3B	Has the CSP defined the authorized bodies and its composition?	- Specific document that includes information about the authorized bodies and its composition
		Q2-ISP-02.3B	Are the security policies and procedures approved by the CSP's top management or by the authorized bodies?	- Top management or authorized bodies signature of the security policies and procedures
ISP-02.4B	The CSP's subject matter experts shall review the policies and procedures for adequacy at least annually, when the global information security policy is updated, and when major changes may affect the security of the cloud service	Q1-ISP-02.4B	Every subject matter has an expert identified?	- Global information security policy document - Organizational structure - Other specific document
		Q2-ISP-02.4B	Every policies and procedures have been reviewed by the related expert at least annually, or when the global information security policy is updated, or when major changes may affect the security of the cloud service?	- Policies and procedures version control and change history

ReqID [3]	Requiremen [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-02.5B	After an update of procedures and policies, they shall be approved before they become effective, and then communicated and made available to internal and external employees	Q1-ISP-02.5B	After an update of procedures and policies, have they been approved before they become effective?	- Signature of the new procedures and policies version
		Q2-ISP-02.5B	After an update of procedures and policies, have they been communicated and made available to internal and external employees?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
ISP-03.1B	The CSP shall maintain a list of exceptions, limited in time, to the security policies and procedures, including associated controls.	Q1-ISP-03.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of exceptions to the security policies and procedures?	- List of exceptions to the security policies and procedures - records of updates of the list of exceptions
		Q2-ISP-03.1B	Does the list of exceptions include associated controls?	- Associated controls in the list of exceptions
		Q3-ISP-03.1B	Are the exceptions defined limited in time?	- Time limitation for each exception
ISP-03.2B	The list of exceptions shall be reviewed at least annually	Q1-ISP-03.2B	Are the list of exceptions reviewed at least annually?	- List of exceptions document version control and change history - List of exceptions document review record

Risk Management

Table 6. Checklist for RM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
RM-01.1B	<p>The CSP shall document policies and procedures in accordance with ISP-02 for the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality, integrity, availability and authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS and assigning risk owners; • Analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk; • Evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling; • Handling of risks through measures, including approval of authorisation and acceptance of residual risks by risk owners; and • Documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results. 	Q1-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document the policies and procedures for Risk management?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document - Risk management procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (it includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS)
		Q3-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS)
		Q4-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS)
		Q5-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS)
		Q6-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the assignment of risk owners?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the assignment of risk owners) - Risk management procedures (includes the assignment of risk owners)
		Q7-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk) - Risk management procedures (includes the analysis of the probability and im-

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				pact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk)
		Q8-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling) - Risk management procedures (includes the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling)
		Q9-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the handling of risks through measures?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the handling of risks through measures) - Risk management procedures
		Q10-RM-01.1B	Does the handling of risks through measures, includes the approval of authorisation and acceptance of residual risks by risk owners?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document - Risk management procedures (includes the handling of risks through measures)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q11-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results) - Risk management procedures (includes the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results)
RM-02.1B	The CSP shall implement the policies and procedures covering risk assessment on the entire perimeter of the cloud service.	Q1-RM-02.1B	Does the CSP implement the policies and procedures covering risk assessment on the entire perimeter of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Records showing the implementation of the policies and procedures covering risk assessment on the entire perimeter of the cloud service
RM-02.2B	The CSP shall make the results of the risk assessment available to relevant stakeholders	Q1-RM-02.2B	Does the CSP make the results of the risk assessment available to relevant stakeholders?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk assessment results - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
RM-02.3B	The CSP shall review and revise the risk assessment at least annually, and after each major change that may affect the security of the cloud service.	Q1-RM-02.3B	Does the CSP review and revise the risk assessment at least annually?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Top management or authorized bodies signature of the risk assessment at least annually - records of this review in logs with dates

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-RM-02.3B	Does the CSP review and revise the risk assessment after each major change that may affect the security of the cloud service?	- List of major changes - Top management or authorized bodies signature of the risk assessment after major changes
RM-03.1B	The CSP shall prioritize risks according to their criticality	Q1-RM-03.1B	Does the CSP shall prioritize risks according to their criticality?	- List of prioritized risks according to their criticality
RM-03.2B	The CSP shall define and implement a plan to treat risks according to their priority level by reducing or avoiding them through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them.	Q1-RM-03.2B	Does the CSP define a risk treatment plan to treat risks according to their priority level?	- Risk treatment plan according to their priority level
		Q2-RM-03.2B	Does the risk treatment plan contemplate the reducing or avoiding the risks through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them?	- Risk treatment plan (contemplates the reducing or avoiding the risks through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them)
		Q3-RM-03.2B	Does the CSP implement the defined risk treatment plan?	Evidences of actions defined in the risk treatment plan
RM-03.3B	The risk treatment plan shall reduce the risk level to a threshold that the risk owners deem acceptable (Residual Risk).	Q1-RM-03.3B	Does the risk treatment plan reduce the risk level to a threshold that the risk owners deem acceptable (Residual Risk)?	- Risk threshold evolution through time.
		Q2-RM-03.3B	Is it defined what a residual risk is?	- Formal and documented definition of "Residual Risk"

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
RM-03.4B	The CSP shall make the risk treatment plan available to relevant stakeholders	Q1-RM-03.4B	Does the CSP make the risk treatment plan available to relevant stakeholders?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk treatment plan - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, the shared risks shall be associated to Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs) and described in the user documentation	Q1-RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, are the shared risks associated to Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of Complementary Customer Controls for the risks shared with the CSC - Traceability between risks shared by CSP and Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs)
		Q1-RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, are the shared risks described in the user documentation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User documentation including the description of the shared risks
RM-03.6B	The CSP shall revise the risk treatment plan every time the risk assessment is revised.	Q1-RM-03.6B	Does the CSP revise the risk treatment plan every time the risk assessment is revised?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk treatment plan version control and change history - Risk treatment plan review record

Human Resources

Table 7. Checklist for HR basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
HR-01.1B	The CSP shall classify information security-sensitive positions according to their level of risk, including positions related to IT administration and to the provisioning of the cloud service in the production environment, and all positions with access to cloud customer data or system components.	Q1-HR-01.1B	Are the security-sensitive positions classified according to their level of risk?	- Competence Position Document or similar - Policy document (roles section)
		Q2-HR-01.1B	Are the IT administration positions included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes the administration positions)
		Q3-HR-01.1B	Are the cloud service provisioning positions included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes the cloud service provisioning positions)
		Q4-HR-01.1B	Are all the positions with access to cloud customer data included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes all the positions with access to cloud customer data)
		Q5-HR-01.1B	Are all the positions with access to system components / assets included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes all the positions with access to system components)
HR-01.2B	The CSP shall include in its employment contracts or on a dedicated code of conduct or ethics an overarching agreement	Q1-HR-01.2B	- Does there exist an overarching agreement containing rules to act ethically in professionals' duties?	Overarching agreement with rules to act ethically

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	from internal and external employees to act ethically in their professional duties.			
		Q2-HR-01.2B	- Is this overarching agreement included in the internal employees' contract or in a dedicated code of conduct or ethics?	Internal employees' contracts or dedicated Code of Conduct/Ethics document
		Q3-HR-01.2B	- Is this overarching agreement included in the external employees' contract or in a dedicated code of conduct or ethics?	Internal employees' contracts or dedicated Code of Conduct/Ethics document
HR-01.3B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement a policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements, including at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verifying whether a violation has occurred; and • Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact 	Q1-HR-01.3B	- Has the CSP documented a policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements?	- Documented Policy, section dedicated to violations, instructions, applicable legal and regulatory requirements
		Q2-HR-01.3B	- Does the documented policy include at least the following aspects? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verifying whether a violation has occurred; and • Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact 	- Documented Policy (includes verifying whether a violation has occurred & Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-HR-01.3B	Has the CSP communicated the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policy communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q4-HR-01.3B	Are there evidences that the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements has been implemented?	-Records related to the policy implementation such as warnings and signed documents in accordance to the what it is defined in the policy for the different levels of violations
HR-01.4B	If disciplinary measures are defined in the policy mentioned in this policy, then the internal and external employees of the CSP shall be informed about possible disciplinary measures and the use of these disciplinary measures shall be appropriately documented.	Q1-HR01.4B	Does the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements contain disciplinary measures?	- HR-03 Policy document
		Q2-HR01.4B	Have the internal employees been informed about possible disciplinary measures?	<p>Mechanisms used to inform internal employees about disciplinary methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-HR01.4B	Have the external employees been informed about possible disciplinary measure?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanisms used to inform external employees about disciplinary methods - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q4-HR01.4	Have the use of the disciplinary measures been appropriately documented?	- Documented disciplinary measures way of use
HR-02.1B	The competency and integrity of all internal and external employees of the CSP with access to cloud customer data or system components under the CSP's responsibility, or who are responsible to provide the cloud service in the production environment shall be reviewed before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01. The extent of the review shall be proportional to the business context, the sensitivity of the information that will be accessed by the employee, and the associated risks.	Q1-HR-02.1B	Are the competency and integrity of all internal employees of the CSP with access to cloud customer data or system components under the CSP's responsibility reviewed before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01?	- Documented review results
		Q2-HR-02.1B	Are the competency and integrity of all internal employees of the CSP that are responsible to provide the cloud service in the production environment reviewed before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01?	'- Documented review results

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-HR-02.1B	Are the competency and integrity of all external employees of the CSP with access to cloud customer data or system components under the CSP's responsibility reviewed before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01?	'- Documented review results
		Q4-HR-02.1B	Are the competency and integrity of all external employees of the CSP that are responsible to provide the cloud service in the production environment reviewed before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01?	'- Documented review results
		Q5-HR-02.1B	Is the extent of this review proportional to the business context, the sensitivity of the information that will be accessed by the employee, and the associated risks?	- Documented review procedure (includes aspects related to the proportionality of the review to the business context, the sensitivity of the information that will be accessed by the employee, and the associated risks)
HR-02.2B	The competency and integrity of internal and external employees of the CSP shall be reviewed before commencement of employment in a position with a higher risk classification than their previous position within the company.	Q1-HR-02.2B	Does the employment terms and conditions of the internal employees oblige to comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures?	- Employment terms and conditions of the internal employees
HR-03.1B	The CSP shall ensure that all internal and external employees are required by their employment terms and conditions to	Q1-HR-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that internal employees comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures?	- Employment terms and conditions - Audit results of internal employees

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures.			
		Q2-HR-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that external employees comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures?	- Employment terms and conditions - Audit results of external employees
HR-03.2B	The CSP shall ensure that the employment terms for all internal and external employees include a non-disclosure provision, which shall cover any information that has been obtained or generated as part of the cloud service, even if anonymised and de-contextualized.	Q1-HR-03.2B	Does the employment terms for all internal employees include a non-disclosure provision?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions for internal employees
		Q2-HR-03.2B	Does the employment terms for all external employees include a non-disclosure provision?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions for external employees
		Q3-HR-03.2	Does the non-disclosure provision cover any information that has been obtained or generated as part of the cloud service, even if anonymised and decontextualized?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions
HR-03.3B	The CSP shall give a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to internal and external employees before granting them any access to customer data, the production environment, or any component thereof	Q1-HR-03.3B	Has the CSP given a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to internal employees before granting them any access to customer data, the production environment, or any component thereof?	- Information security policies and procedure presentation + delivery evidences

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-HR-03.3B	Has the CSP given a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to external employees before granting them any access to customer data, the production environment, or any component thereof?	- Information security policies and procedure presentation + delivery evidences
HR-04.1B	<p>The CSP shall define a security awareness and training program that covers the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling system components used to provide the cloud service in the production environment in accordance with applicable policies and procedures; • Handling cloud customer data in accordance with applicable policies and instructions and applicable legal and regulatory requirements; • Information about the current threat situation; and • Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents. 	Q1-HR-04.1B	Has the CSP defined a security awareness and training program?	- Documented security awareness and training program

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-HR-04.1B	<p>Does the defined security awareness and training program contains at least the following topics?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling system components used to provide the cloud service in the production environment in accordance with applicable policies and procedures; • Handling cloud customer data in accordance with applicable policies and instructions and applicable legal and regulatory requirements; • Information about the current threat situation; and • Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents. 	- Security awareness and training program (includes Handling system components, Handling cloud customer data, Information about the current threat situation and Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents)
HR-04.2B	The CSP shall review their security awareness and training program based on changes to policies and instructions and the current threat situation	Q1-HR-04.2B	Is the security awareness and training program kept updated according to the changes to policies and instructions and the current threat situation?	- Documented history of the security and awareness training program with references to policies/instructions/Threat situation
HR-04.3B	The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them	Q1-HR-04.3B	Have all the CSP employees received the defined security awareness and training program?	- Training delivery records
HR-05.1B	The CSP shall communicate to internal and external employees their ongoing responsibilities relating to information security when their employment is terminated or changed.	Q1-HR-05.1B	Does the CSP communicate to internal employees their ongoing responsibilities relating to information security when their employment is terminated or changed.	- Employee termination/position change document

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-HR-05.1	Does the CSP communicate to external employees their ongoing responsibilities relating to information security when their employment is terminated or changed.	- Employee termination/position change document
HR-05.2B	The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of internal and external employees when their employment is terminated or changed	Q1-HR-05.2B	Have the CSP defined a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of internal and external employees when their employment is terminated or changed?	- Documented specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of internal and external employees when their employment is terminated or changed
		Q2-HR-05.2B	Is this procedure applied to internal employees?	- Evidence of the new access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets to internal employees
		Q3-HR-05.2B	Is this procedure applied to external employees?	- Evidence of the new access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets to external employees
HR-06.1B	The CSP shall ensure that non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements are agreed with internal employees, external service providers and suppliers	Q1-HR-06.1B	Does the CSP have a non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers	- Documented Non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-HR-06.1B	Does the CSP ensure the agreement between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers based on the defined non-disclosure agreement?	- Signed non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers

Asset management

Table 8. Checklist for AM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
AM-01.1B	The CSP shall document and implement policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets	Q1-AM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets?	- Policies and procedures document
		Q2-AM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement the defined policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets?	- Documented Inventory of assets
AM-01.2B	The CSP shall record for each asset the information needed to apply the risk management procedure defined in RM-01.	Q1-AM-01.2B	Does the CSP record for each asset the information needed to apply the risk management procedure defined in RM-01?	- Documented Information needed for each asset to apply risk management in the inventory of assets

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
AM-02.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures as defined in ISP-02 for acceptable use and safe handling of assets. When removable media is used in the technical infrastructure or for IT administration tasks, this media shall be dedicated to a single use.	Q1-AM-02.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets?	- Policies and procedures document - Global security policies
		Q2-AM-02.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets?	- Evidences related to the policies and procedures communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-AM-02.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets?	NB. Difficult to provide an evidence (indeterminism of "acceptable use")
		Q4-AM-02.1B	When removable media is used in the technical infrastructure or for IT administration tasks, are this media dedicated to a single use?	Evidence that this removable media is used e.g. only for backup
AM-03.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures	Q1-AM-03.1B	Does the CSP document a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Documented Hardware commissioning procedure

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-AM-03.1B	Does the CSP communicate procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Internal communication
		Q3-AM-03.1B	Does CSP implement a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Evidences related to procedure for the commissioning of hardware implementation: - HW commissioning records / Implementation checklist or equivalent
AM-03.2B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, including the complete and permanent deletion of the data or the proper destruction of the media and requiring approval based on applicable policies.	Q1-AM-03.2B	Does the CSP document a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Documented Hardware decommissioning procedure
		Q2-AM-03.2B	Does the CSP communicate procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Internal communication

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-AM-03.2B	Does CSP implement a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Evidences related to procedure for the decommissioning of hardware implementation: - HW decommissioning records / Implementation checklist or equivalent
		Q4-AM-03.2B	Does the decommissioning procedure include the complete and permanent deletion of the data or the proper destruction of the media and requiring approval based on applicable policies?	Decommissioning Procedure Evidences of procedure application in real cases
AM-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure and document that all internal and external employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02	Q1-AM-04.1B	How the CSP ensure that internal and external employees are committed to the established policy and procedures related to assets commissioning and decommissioning?	-Evidences of actions to ensure employees commitment
		Q2-AM-04.1B	Does the CSP document this commitment in some way?	- Employee commitment Document
AM-04.2B	The procedure mentioned in HR-06.2 shall include steps to ensure that all assets under custody of an employee are returned upon termination of employment.	Q1-AM-04.2B	Does the Confidentiality Agreement between the CSP and each employee include a clause related to the return of assets under custody of the employee a upon termination of employment?	- Specific clause in the Confidentiality Agreement signed with each employee

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
AM-05.1B	The CSP shall define an asset classification scheme that reflects for each asset the protection needs of the information it processes, stores, or transmits	Q1-AM-05.1B	For every asset included in the Asset Inventory, has the CSP defined an asset classification scheme that reflects the protection needs of the information it processes, stores, or transmits?	- Assets classification scheme in the Assets Inventory or in a separate document
AM-05.2B	When applicable, the CSP shall label all assets according to their classification in the asset classification scheme	Q1-AM-05.2B	Has the CSP labelled (when applicable) each assets according to the assets classification scheme?	- List of assets linked to their labels / tags and other configuration information - Photograph (or other recording means) of the labelled assets - Assets classification Scheme

Physical security

Table 9. Checklist for PS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PS-01.1B	The CSP shall define security perimeters in the buildings and premises related to the cloud service provided	Q1-PS-01.1B	Does the CSP define security perimeters in the buildings related to the cloud service provided?	- Building plans - Security perimeter plans - A CSP shall establish secure areas to protect valuable information and assets that only authorized people can access
		Q2-PS-01.1B	Does the CSP define security perimeters in the premises related to the cloud service provided?	- Building plans - Security perimeter plans, identifying which are the ones concerning the cloud service

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PS-01.2B	The CSP shall define at least two security areas, with one covering all buildings and premises and one covering sensitive activities such as the buildings and premises hosting the information system for the production of the service	Q1-PS-01.2B	Does the CSP define a security area covering all buildings and premises?	-Documented security area plan, establishing the two security areas, as per the requirement and who has access to them and per which terms
		Q2-PS-01.2B	Does the CSP define a security area covering sensitive activities such as the buildings and premises hosting the information system for the production of the service?	-Documented security area plan
PS-01.3B	The CSP shall define and communicate a set of security requirements for each security area in a policy according to ISP-02	Q1-PS-01.3b	Does the CSP define a set of security requirements for each security area in a policy according to ISP-02 (Information Security Policy)?	- Documented security requirements for each security area - Documented physical policy
		Q2-PS-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate the set of security requirements?	- Evidences related to the set of security requirements communication: - Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
PS-02.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 related to the physical access control to the security areas	Q1-PS-02.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas?	-Documented policies and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	matching the requirements defined in PS-01 and based on the principles defined in IAM-01			
		Q2-PS-02.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas communication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-PS-02.1B	Does the CSP shall implement policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas?	- Access control systems to prevent unauthorised access (ie: EACS, intercoms, videophones, CCTV cameras, mechanical locking devices operated by keys or codes, etc.)
PS-02.2B	The access control policy shall require at least one authentication factor for accessing any non-public area	Q1-PS-02.2B	Does the access control policy require at least one authentication factor for accessing any non-public area?	- Authentication factors (ie: Fingerprint, PIN, etc.)
PS-02.3B	The access control policy shall describe the physical access control derogations in case of emergency	Q1-PS-02.3B	Does the access control policy describe the physical access control derogations in case of emergency?	- Documented description of the physical access control derogations in case of emergency

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PS-02.4B	The CSP shall display at the entrance of all non-public perimeters a warning concerning the limits and access conditions to these perimeters	Q1-PS-02.4B	Does the CSP display at the entrance of all non-public perimeters a warning concerning the limits and access conditions to these perimeters?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wallchats - Specific warning signals - Etc.
PS-02.5B	The CSP shall protect security perimeters with security measures to detect and prevent unauthorised access in a timely manner so that it does not compromise the information security of the cloud service	Q1-PS-02.5B	Does the CSP protect security perimeters with security measures to detect and prevent unauthorised access in a timely manner so that it does not compromise the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CCTV (closed circuit television) Security System. - Access control systems. Access control systems serve to restrict entry only to authorized personnel. - Motion sensors. - Fiber optic detection systems. - Ground Radar Systems. - Microwave barriers. - Electrified fences. - Microphone cable fence disturbance sensors. - Etc.
PS-03.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate, and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 concerning work in non-public areas	Q1-PS-03.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures concerning the work in non-public areas?	-Documented policies and procedures
		Q2-PS-03.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures concerning work in non-public areas?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policies and procedures concerning work in non-public areas communication: -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-PS-03.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning work in non-public areas?	-Access control systems to prevent unauthorised access (ie: EACS, intercoms, videophones, CCTV cameras, mechanical locking devices operated by keys or codes, etc.)
PS-04.1B	<p>The CSP shall document, communicate, and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 concerning the protection of equipment and including at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage; • Protecting equipment during maintenance operations; • Protecting equipment holding customer data during transport. 	Q1-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage?	-Documented policies and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Power and telecommunications lines undergrounded - Power cables isolated - Installation of reinforced ducts and locked rooms or boxes at inspection and termination points - Electromagnetic shielding for cable protection - Access controlled to cable rooms and patch panels - Etc.
		Q4-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations?	- Documented policies and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q5-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q6-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service interval recommendations and supplier specifications - List of authorized maintenance personnel - Records of all failures, real or suspected, as well as all preventive and corrective maintenance - Maintenance requirements required by insurance policies
		Q7-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding customer data during transport.	- Documented policies and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q8-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding customer data during transport.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding customer data during transport communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q9-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding customer data during transport.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable transport or courier. It can also be an approved transport or courier, in agreement with the policies and procedures (see below) - List of authorized couriers - Procedures to verify the identity of couriers; - Packaging protect specifications - Records identifying the content of the media, the protection applied, as well as reflecting the moments of transfer to custodians and reception at destination.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PS-04.2B	The CSP shall use encryption on the removable media and the backup media intended to move between security areas according to the sensitivity of the data stored on the media	Q1-PS-04.2B	Does the CSP use encryption on the removable media intended to move between security areas?	- Compliant encryption algorithms and tools (ie Self Encrypting USB Drives, Media Encryption Software, File Encryption Software) - Secure password management tool
		Q2-PS-04.2B	Does the CSP shall use encryption on the backup media intended to move between security areas?	- Backup software
		Q3-PS-04.2B	Is the level of encryption according to the sensitivity of the data stored on the media?	- Encrypted logs
PS-05.1B	The CSP shall document and communicate a set of security requirements related to external and environmental threats in a policy according to SP-02, addressing the following risks in accordance with the applicable legal and contractual requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faults in planning; • Unauthorised access; • Insufficient surveillance; • Insufficient air-conditioning; • Fire and smoke; • Water; • Power failure; and • Air ventilation and filtration. 	Q1-PS-05.1B	Does the CSP document a set of security requirements related to external and environmental threats in a policy according to Information Security Policies (SP-02)?	- Documented policy

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-PS-05.1B	Does the CSP communicate the policy?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences related to the security requirements related to external and environmental threats in a policy communication: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address faults in planning?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (faults in planning)
		Q4-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address unauthorised access?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (unauthorised access)
		Q5-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address insufficient surveillance?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (insufficient surveillance)
		Q6-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address insufficient air-conditioning?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (what to do when there is a lack of insufficient air-conditioning - e.g. high temperature)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q7-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address fire and smoke?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (fire and smoke)
		Q8-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address water?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (water)
		Q9-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address power failure?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (power failure)
		Q10-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address air ventilation and filtration?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (air ventilation and filtration)

Operational security

Table 10. Checklist for OPS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-01.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources), which shall include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload	Q1-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP document procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	- Capacity plan - Specific capacity procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-OPS-01.1B	Do procedures include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload?	- Capacity plan (encompasses future capacity requirements) - Specific capacity procedures
		Q3-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	- Capacity plan audit
OPS-01.2B	The CSP shall meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks or personnel and IT resources outages	Q1-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks?	- Monitoring reports - contractual agreements - Non-conformities to the contract (if there are non-compliances)
		Q2-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of IT resources outages?	- Monitoring reports - Non-conformities to the contract/SLA (if there are non-compliances) - contractual agreements
OPS-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement technical and organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement	Q1-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP define technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Multidimensional QoS prediction methods
		Q2-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP define organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Multi-dimensional QoS measures
		Q4-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report
OPS-03.1B	The CSP shall enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs	Q1-OPS-03.1B	Does the CSP enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs?	- Contractual agreement - SLA - Privileges to use the monitoring and control tools
OPS-04.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of system-specific protection mechanisms; • Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment; and • Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment. 	Q1-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the use of system-specific protection mechanisms?	- Documented policies and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the use of system-specific protection mechanisms?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the use of system-specific protection mechanisms?	- System-specific protection mechanisms - System-specific protection mechanism deployment report - Audit report - policies and procedures
		Q4-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q5-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallcharts - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q6-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP - Operating protection programs deployment report - Audit report
		Q7-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q8-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q9-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment - Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment deployment report - Audit report
OPS-05.1B	The CSP shall deploy malware protection, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the cloud service in the production environment, according to policies and procedures	Q1-OPS-05.1B	Does the CSP deploy malware protection, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the cloud service in the production environment?	- Malware protection programs deployed

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-OPS-05.1B	Is the deploy of malware protection according to policies and procedures?	- Documented policies and procedures for malware protection - Malware deployment report
OPS-06.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery	Q1-OPS-06.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q1-OPS-06.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-OPS-06.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A filled form or screenshot identifying which information was requested to be backed up, the requester, the date of request, the date when the backup was performed, the result of the backup procedure (successful / fail) and where the backup was stored. - A general schedule of the backup to be performed, identifying which information is planned to be backed up, the requester, the dates planned for backup, and where the backup must be stored
OPS-07.1B	The CSP shall document and implement technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups in accordance to the policies and procedures defined in OPS- 06	Q1-OPS-07.1B	Does the CSP document technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups?	- Documented technical and organizational measures
		Q2-OPS-07.1B	Does the CSP implement technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups?	- Documented technical and organizational measures report
		Q3-OPS-07.1B	Are the technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups in accordance to the policies and procedures defined in OPS- 06?	- Documented conformity report

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-08.1B	The CSP shall test the restore procedures at least annually	Q1-OPS-08.1B	Does the CSP test the restore procedures at least annually?	' - A filled form or screenshot identifying which information was requested to be restored, the requester, the date of request, the date when the restore was performed, and the result of the restore procedure (successful / fail)
OPS-09.1B	The CSP shall transfer backup data to a remote location or transport them on backup media to a remote location	Q1-OPS-09.1B	Does the CSP transfer backup data to a remote location or transport them on backup media to a remote location?	- Data transport report
OPS-09.2B	When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM- 02).	Q1-OPS-09.2B	When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, do the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM- 02)?	- Data transport report (encompasses an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02))
OPS-10.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging and monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility	Q1-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q2-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging of events on system components under its responsibility?	-Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented Reports '-Logs

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q5-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility??	-Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q6-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented policies and procedures -Logs
OPS-11.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data	Q1-OPS-11.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q1-OPS-11.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data?	-Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q1-OPS-11.1B	The CSP shall implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data?	- Records derived from the implementation of the policies and procedures covering the governance of the secure handling of derived data - Logs

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-12.1B	The CSP shall monitor log data in order to identify events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.	Q1-OPS-12.1B	Does the CSP monitor log data in order to identify events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements?	- Documented monitoring of log data (Logs) - Documented security incidents
		Q2-OPS-12.1B	Are identified events reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation?	- Security incidents notification event report
OPS-13.1B	The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation	Q1-OPS-13.1B	Does the CSP store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation?	- Log data Database
OPS-13.2B	The communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers shall be authenticated and protected in integrity and confidentiality	Q1-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers authenticated in integrity?	Logs
		Q2-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers authenticated in confidentiality?	Logs
		Q3-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers protected in integrity?	Logs
		Q4-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers protected in confidentiality?	Logs
OPS-13.3B	Log data shall be deleted when it is no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected	Q1-OPS-13.3B	Are log data deleted when it is no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected?	- Log data deletion record
OPS-14.1B	The log data generated allows an unambiguous identification of user accesses at the CSC level to support analysis in the event of an incident	Q1-OPS-14.1B	Does the log data generated allows an unambiguous identification of user accesses at the CSC level to support analysis in the event of an incident?	Logs

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-15.1B	The CSP shall restrict to authorized users only the access to system components used for logging and monitoring under their responsibility	Q1-OPS-15.1B	Does the CSP restrict to authorized users only the access to system components used for logging and monitoring under their responsibility?	- Documented authorized access users list
OPS-15.2B	Changes to the logging and monitoring configuration are made in accordance with applicable policies (cf. CCM-01)	Q1-OPS-15.2B	Are changes to the logging and monitoring configuration made in accordance with applicable policies (cf. CCM-01)?	- Cross References between changes to the logging and monitoring configuration and policies for changes to information systems
OPS-16.1B	The CSP shall monitor the system components for logging and monitoring under its responsibility, and shall automatically report failures to the responsible departments for assessment and remediation	Q1-OPS-16.1B	Does the CSP monitor the system components for logging and monitoring under its responsibility?	- Documented system components monitor report
		Q2-OPS-16.1B	Does the CSP automatically report failures to the responsible departments for assessment and remediation?	- Automatizad failures report
OPS-17.1B	The CSP shall document, communicated and implement in accordance to ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service	Q1-OPS-17.1B	Does the CSP document in accordance to ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q2-OPS-17.1B	Does the CSP communicate in accordance to ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service?	-Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-OPS-17.1B	Does the CSP implement in accordance to ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service?	- Documented list of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service - Vulnerabilities addressing report
OPS-17.2B	The CSP shall use a scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities that includes at least “critical” and “high” classes of vulnerabilities	Q1-OPS-17.2B	Does the CSP shall use a scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities?	- Documented scoring system
		Q2-OPS-17.3	Does the scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities includes at least “critical” and “high” classes of vulnerabilities?	- Classes of vulnerabilities identified in the scoring system. ("critical" & "high" at least)
OPS-18.1B	The CSP shall publish and maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility	Q1-OPS-18.1B	Does the CSP publish a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility?	-WEB -eMail - etc.
		Q2-OPS-18.1B	Does the CSP maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility?	- Register of vulnerabilities update date

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-18.2B	The online register shall indicate at least the following information for every vulnerability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A presentation of the vulnerability following an industry-accepted scoring system; • A description of the remediation options for that vulnerability; • Information on the availability of updates or patches for that vulnerability; • Information about the remediation or deployment of patches or updates by the CSP or CSC, including detailed instructions for operations to be performed by the CSC. 	Q1-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability a presentation of the vulnerability following an industry-accepted scoring system?	- Vulnerability online register
		Q2-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability a description of the remediation options for that vulnerability?	- Vulnerability online register
		Q3-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability information on the availability of updates or patches for that vulnerability?	- Vulnerability online register
		Q4-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability information about the remediation or deployment of patches or updates by the CSP or CSC, including detailed instructions for operations to be performed by the CSC?	- Vulnerability online register
OPS-18.3B	The CSP shall publish and maintain a list of pointers to online registers published by its subservice providers and suppliers, or integrate regularly into its own online register the content of these	Q1-OPS-18.3B	Does the CSP publish a list of pointers to online registers published by its subservice providers and suppliers?	- List of pointers to online registers -WEB -eMail - etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	online registers relevant to the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility.			
		Q2-OPS-18.3B	Does the CSP maintain a list of pointers to online registers published by its subservice providers and suppliers? Or does the CSP integrate regularly the content of these online registers relevant to the cloud service into its own online register?	- Register of list of pointers to online registers update date
OPS-18.4B	The CSP shall consult regularly the online registers published by its subservice providers and suppliers, analyse the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service, and handle them according to the vulnerability handling process (cf. OPS-17)	Q1-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP consult regularly the online registers of vulnerabilities published by its subservice providers and suppliers?	N.B.Difficult to provide an evidence
		Q2-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP shall analyse the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service?	- Documented analysis of the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service
		Q3-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP handle the vulnerabilities according to the vulnerability handling process (cf. OPS-17)?	Audit records concerning to the handle vulnerabilities
OPS-19.1B	The CSP shall perform on a regular basis tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the cloud service, in accordance with policies for handling vulnerabilities (cf. OPS-17)	Q1-OPS-19.1B	Does the CSP perform on a regular basis tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the cloud service?	- Test report

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-OPS-19.1B	Are basis tests made in accordance with policies for handling vulnerabilities (cf. OPS-17)?	- Audit records concerning to the handle vulnerabilities
OPS-20.1B	The CSP shall regularly measure, analyse and assess the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness	Q1-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly measure the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures review date
		Q2-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly analyse the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures review date
		Q3-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly assess the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures review date
OPS-21.1B	The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards	Q1-OPS-21.1B	Does the CSP harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards?	- Documented hardens to all the system components under its responsibility - Changes in the system components (encompasses the hardens)
OPS-21.2B	The hardening requirements for each system component shall be documented	Q1-OPS-21.2B	Are the hardening requirements for each system component documented?	- Documented hardening requirements for each system component
OPS-22.1B	The CSP shall segregate the CSC data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data	Q1-OPS-22.1B	Does the CSP segregate the CSC data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data?	- Documented risk analysis - CSC data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources

Identity and Access Management

Table 11. Checklist for IAM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IAM-01.1B	<p>The CSP shall document, communicate and make available role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources, according to ISP-02 and based on the business and security requirements of the CSP, in which at least the following aspects are covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions • Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need-to-know” principle. • Use of a role-based mechanism for the assignment of access rights • Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights • Dedicated rules for users with privileged access • Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights 	Q1-IAM-01.1B	Have the CSP documented a role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources?	- Documented role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources
		Q2-IAM-01.1B	Are the above documented policies and procedures aligned with the Global Information Security Policy defined in ISP-02?	- Cross references between role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources and Global Information Security Policy
		Q3-IAM-01.1B	Are the above documented policies and procedures based on the business and security requirements of the CSP?	DIFFICULT TO PROVIDE A VALID EVIDENCE

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				'- Policies and procedures review records (Approval signature)
		Q4-IAM-01.1B	Does the above documented policies and procedure contains at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions • Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need-to-know” principle. • Use of a role-based mechanism for the assignment of access rights • Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights • Dedicated rules for users with privileged access • Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights 	- Documented role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources (include these five topics) - Policies and procedures review records
IAM-01.2B	The CSP shall link the access control policy defined in IAM-01.1 with the physical access control policy defined in PS-02.1, to guarantee that the access to the premises where information is located is also controlled.	Q1-IAM-01.2B	Does the IAM-01.1 documented policy and the PS-02.1 documented policy make cross reference between them?	- Cross references between IAM-01-1 policy and PS-02.1 policy
IAM-02.1B	The CSP shall document policies for managing accounts, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters for making access control decisions Assignment of unique usernames • Definition of the different types of accounts sup- 	Q1-IAM-02.1B	Are the policies for managing accounts documented?	- Documented policies for managing accounts

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	ported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events leading to blocking and revoking accounts 			
		Q2-IAM-02.1B	Are the policies for managing accounts aligned with ISP-02 policy?	- Policies review records
		Q3-IAM-02.1B	Does the documented policies for managing accounts contain at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters for making access control decisions • Assignment of unique usernames • Definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type • Events leading to blocking and revoking accounts 	- Documented policies (encompass assignment of unique usernames, definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type & events leading to blocking and revoking accounts) - Policies review records
IAM-02.2B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures for managing personal user accounts and access rights to internal and external employees that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts	Q1-IAM-02.2B	Are the procedures for managing personal user accounts and access rights to internal and external employees documented?	- Documented procedures for managing personal user accounts and access rights to internal and external employees
		Q2-IAM-02.2B	Are the previous documented policies comply the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-IAM-02.2B	Are these procedures implemented for internal employees?	' - Personal user account and access rights for internal employees
		Q4-IAM-02.2B	Are these procedures implemented for external employees?	- Personal user account and access rights for external employees
IAM-02.3B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures for managing non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts	Q1-IAM-02.3B	Are the procedures for managing non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights documented?	- Documented procedures for managing non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights
		Q2-IAM-02.3B	Are the previous documented policies comply the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result
		Q3-IAM-02.3B	Are these procedures implemented?	- Non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights
IAM-02.4B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures for managing technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service that comply with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts	Q1-IAM-02.4B	Are the procedures for managing technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service documented?	' - Documented procedures for managing technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service
		Q2-IAM-02.4B	Are the previous documented policies comply the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result
		Q3-IAM-02.4B	Are these procedures implemented?	- Technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				the operation of the cloud service
IAM-02.5B	The CSP shall be able to provide, for a given user account, whether it falls under the responsibility of the CSP or of the CSC, as well as the list of the access rights granted to that account.	Q1-IAM-02.5B	Can the CSP provide for a given user account, whether it falls under the responsibility of the CSP or of the CSC?	- Fault register associated to a user account in which it is specified if the faults responsibility is of CSP or CSC
		Q2-IAM-02.5B	Can the CSP provide for a given user account, the list of the access rights granted to that account?	- List of access right granted associated to a user account that has fault
IAM-03.1B	The CSP shall define and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity.	Q1-IAM-03.1B	Does the CSP defined a mechanism that automatically block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity?	- Documented description of the mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity
		Q2-IAM-03.1B	Is the "certain period of inactivity" quantified and documented somewhere?	- Document in which is specified the "certain period of time" after which the user account is automatically blocked
		Q3-IAM-03.1B	Does the automated mechanism in place executed when some user account overcome the specified period of time?	- Evidences of blocked user accounts that meet the defined requirements
IAM-03.2B	The CSP shall define and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts	Q1-IAM-03.2B	Does the CSP defined a mechanism that automatically block user accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts?	- Documented description of the mechanism to block user accounts
		Q2-IAM-03.2B	Is the "certain number of failed authentication attempts" quantified and documented somewhere?	- Document in which is specified the "certain number of failed authentication attempts" after which the user

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				account is automatically blocked
		Q3-IAM-03.2B	Does the automated mechanism in place executed after the specified certain number of failed authentication attempts?	- Evidences of blocked user accounts that meet the defined requirements
IAM-04.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to grant, update, and revoke to a user account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service, and these procedures shall be compliant with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing access rights	Q1-IAM-04.1B	Has the CSP documented procedures to grant, update, and revoke to a user account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service?	- Documented procedures to grant, update, and revoke to a user account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service
		Q2-IAM-04.1B	Are these documented procedures compliant with the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing access rights?	- Procedure assessment results
		Q3-IAM-04.1B	Are these procedures implemented within the CSP?	- Examples of user accounts to which access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service have been granted, updated, revoked
IAM-04.2B	The CSP shall document and implement a procedure to timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change.	Q1-IAM-04.2B	Has the CSP documented procedures to timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change?	- Documented procedures o timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-IAM-04.2B	Are the previous documented procedures implemented for internal employees?	- Example of internal employees whose access rights have been updated/revoked when their role and responsibilities has changed
		Q3-IAM-04.2B	Are the previous documented procedures implemented for external employees?	- Example of external employees whose access rights have been updated/revoked when their role and responsibilities has changed
IAM-05.1B	The CSP shall review the access rights of all the user accounts under its responsibility at least once a year to ensure that they still correspond to the current needs	Q1-IAM-05.1B	Does the CSP periodically review the access rights of all user accounts under its responsibility?	- Access rights review results
		Q2-IAM-05.1B	Is the previous review executed at least annually for all the user accounts under the CSP responsibility?	- Review execution dates of the last 2/3 years
IAM-06.1B	Shared accounts under the responsibility of the CSP shall be assigned only to internal or external employees	Q1-IAM-06.1B	Are the shared accounts under the responsibility of the CSP assigned only to internal or external employees?	- Assignment of the shared accounts
IAM-07.1B	The CSP shall document and implement a policy and procedures about authentication mechanisms, covering at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; • The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; • The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; 	Q1-IAM-07.1B	Have the CSP documented policy and procedures about authentication mechanisms?	- Documented policy and procedures

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and • Rules on the required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules; 			
		Q2-IAM-07.1B	<p>Does these policy and procedures cover at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; • The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; • The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; • Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and • Rules on the required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented policy and procedures (encompass the five topics) - Documented policy and procedures review records
		Q3-IAM-07.1B	Are these policy and procedures implemented within the CSP organization?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logs -Databases or any other software asset
IAM-07.2B	The access to all environments of the CSP shall be authenticated, including non-production environments.	Q1-IAM-07.2B	Is the access to all the CSP environment authenticated?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access Logs to the -production environment, in order to

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				see the authentication protocol applied to production environment
		Q2-IAM-07.2B	Are the non-production environment also included in the previous authentication?	- Access Logs to the non-production environment, in order to see the authentication protocol applied to non production environment
IAM-07.3B	All authentication mechanisms shall include a mechanism to block an account after a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts	Q1-IAM-07.3B	Does every authentication mechanism in place within CSP include a mechanism to block an account after a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts?	- If this is something "static": documents that for each authentication mechanism document the blocking mechanism - If this is something "dynamic": examples of blocked account due to unsuccessful attempts
		Q2-IAM-07.3B	Is somewhere documented for every authentication mechanism in place within the CSP the "predefined number of unsuccessful attempts"?	- Document that for each authentication mechanism the blocking mechanism and quantified the number of unsuccessful attempts
IAM-08.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and make available to all users under its responsibility rules and recommendations for the management of credentials, including at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-reuse of credentials • Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize 	Q1-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP documented rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	- Document with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for renewal of passwords • Rules on storage of passwords 			
		Q2-IAM-08.1B	Does the previous document contain at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-reuse of credentials • Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize • Recommendations for renewal of passwords • Rules on storage of passwords 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Document with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials (encompass the four topics) - Document with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials review records
		Q3-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP communicated to all users under its responsibility the rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication mechanism: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q4-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP made available to all users under its responsibility the rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Examples of documents with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials provided by sampled users
IAM-08.2B	Passwords shall be only stored using cryptographically strong hash functions (cf. CKM-01)	Q1-IAM-08.2B	Are all the passwords stored using cryptographically strong hash functions according to the policy defined in CKM-01?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Example of stored passwords randomly selected

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IAM-08.3B	If cryptographic authentication mechanisms are used, they shall follow the policies and procedures from CKM-01.	Q1-IAM-08.3B	If cryptographic authentication mechanisms are used, do they follow the policies and procedures specified in CKM-01?	- Example of cryptographic authentication mechanisms randomly selected + Review results against CKM-01 policies
IAM-09.1B	The CSP shall implement sufficient partitioning measures between the information system providing the cloud service and its other information systems	Q1-IAM-09.1B	Have the CSP implemented partitioning measures between the information system providing the cloud service and its other information systems?	- Example of partitioning measures randomly identified
		Q2-IAM-09.1B	Are the partitioning measures sufficient?	N.B. Not possible to demonstrate with the current level of objectiveness
IAM-09.2B	The CSP shall implement suitable measures for partitioning between the CSCs	Q1-IAM-09.2B	Did the CSP implement measures for partitioning between the CSCs?	- Example of partitioning measures between CSCs randomly identified
		Q2-IAM-09.2B	Are the implemented measures suitable?	N.B. Not possible to demonstrate with the current level of objectiveness

Cryptography & Key management

Table 12. Checklist for CKM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CKM-01.1B	<p>The CSP shall document, communicate, make available and implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols • Requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys • Consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements 	Q1-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	-Documents policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management (encompasses the three aspects)
		Q2-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	<p>- Communication mechanism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP make available policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	- Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Etc.
		Q4-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	- Audit records / Logs
		Q5-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols?	- Policies (describe usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols)
		Q6-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys?	- Policies (describe requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys)
		Q7-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements?	- Policies (describe consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements)
CKM-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of cloud customer data over public networks in order to protect the	Q1-CKM-02.1B	Does the CSP define strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of cloud customer data over public networks?	- Encryption mechanisms design

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of data.			
		Q2-CKM-02.1	Does the CSP implement strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of cloud customer data over public networks?	- Audit records - Examples of encrypted data
CKM-03.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures and technical safeguards to protect the confidentiality of cloud customers' data during storage, according to ISP-02	Q1-CKM-03.1B	Does the CSP document procedures and technical safeguards to protect cloud customers' data during storage according to ISP-02?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards to encrypt cloud customers' data during storage
		Q2-CKM-03.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards to protect cloud customers' data during storage?	- Audit records - Examples of encrypted data
CKM-03.2B	The CSP shall notify customers of updates of these procedures and technical safeguards and to changes in the storage of customer data that may affect the confidentiality of the data.	Q1-CKM-03.2B	Does the CSP notify customers about any updates to technical safeguards and to the procedures that protect the confidentiality of customers' data during storage that may affect the confidentiality of the data.	- Documented notifications to customers (email, reports, web, etc.)
		Q2-CKM-03.2B	Does the CSP notify customers about any changes in the storage of customer data that may affect the confidentiality of the data?	- Documented notifications to customers (email, reports, web, etc.)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CKM-04.1B	<p>Procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP shall include at least the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications; • Issuing and obtaining public-key certificates; • Provisioning and activation of the keys; • Secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access; • Changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised; • Handling of compromised keys; and • Withdrawal and deletion of keys; 	Q1-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP shall include a generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include a generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include issuing and obtaining public-key certificates?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include issuing and obtaining public-key certificates) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
		Q3-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include provisioning and activation of the keys?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include provisioning and activation of the keys) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
		Q5-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q6-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include handling of compromised keys?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include handling of compromised keys) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
		Q7-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include withdrawal and deletion of keys?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include withdrawal and deletion of keys) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record

Communications Security

Table 13. Checklist for CS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CS-01.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks and to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems, in accordance with ISP-02	Q1-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP document technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Documented technical safeguards
		Q2-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Intranet - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Event log and monitoring to allow the recording and detection of actions that could affect, or be relevant, for information security - Audit report
		Q4-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP document technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	- Documented technical safeguards
		Q5-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	- Intranet - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q6-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	- Event log and monitoring to allow the recording and detection of actions that could affect, or be relevant, for information security - Audit report
CS-02-1B	<p>The CSP shall document, communicate, make available and implement specific security requirements to connect within its network, including at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when the security zones are to be separated and when the cloud customers are to be logically or physically segregated; • what communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case; • how the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level; • what internal, cross-location communication is permitted; and • what cross-network communication is allowed. 	Q1-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP document specific security requirements to connect within its network?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP communicate specific security requirements to connect within its network?	- Communication mechanism: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP make available specific security requirements to connect within its network?	- Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Etc.
		Q4-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP implement specific security requirements to connect within its network?	- Audit records
		Q5-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address when the security zones are to be separated and when the cloud customers are to be logically or physically segregated?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
		Q6-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
		Q7-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address how the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q8-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what internal, cross-location communication is permitted?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
		Q9-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what cross-network communication is allowed?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
CS-03.1B	The CSP shall distinguish between trusted and untrusted networks, based on a risk assessment	Q1-CS-03.1B	Does the CSP distinguish between trusted and untrusted networks?	- Documented list of trusted and untrusted networks
		Q2-CS-03.1B	Is that distinction based on a risk assessment?	- Documented risk assessment
CS-03.2B	The CSP shall separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for internal and external network areas (and DMZ, if applicable)	Q1-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for internal network areas?	- Documented network topology
		Q2-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for external network areas?	- Documented network topology
		Q3-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for DMZ, if applicable?	- Documented network topology
CS-03.3B	The CSP shall design and configure both physical and virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)	Q1-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP shall design virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)?	- Documented physical network environments design

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP shall design virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)?	- Documented virtualized network environments design
		Q3-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP configure physical network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)	- Documented physical network environments configuration
		Q4-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP configure virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)	- Documented virtualized network environments configuration
CS-03.4B	The CSP shall review at specified intervals the business justification for using all services, protocols, and ports. This review shall also include the compensatory measures used for protocols that are considered insecure	Q1-CS-03.4B	Does the CSP review at specified intervals the business justification for using all services, protocols, and ports?	- Documented review records (last 2/3 years)
		Q2-CS-03.4B	Does this review also include the compensatory measures used for protocols that are considered insecure?	- Documented review records (include the compensatory measures used for protocols that are considered insecure)
CS-04.1B	The CSP shall define and implement separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles	Q1-CS-04.1B	Does the CSP define separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles	- Audit records
CS-04.2B	The CSP shall logically or physically separate the networks for administration from the CSCs' networks	Q1-CS-04.2B	Does the CSP logically or physically separate the networks for administration from the CSCs' networks?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design
CS-04.3B	The CSP shall segregate physically or logically the networks used to migrate or create virtual machines	Q1-CS-04.3B	Does the CSP segregate physically or logically the networks used to migrate or create virtual machines?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design
CS-05.1B	The CSP shall define, document and implement separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers.	Q1-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP define separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers?	- List of separation mechanisms at network level
		Q2-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP document separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers?	- Documented separation mechanisms design at network level
		Q3-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP implement separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers?	- Audit records
CS-06.1B	The CSP shall maintain up-to-date all documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service	Q1-CS-06.1B	Does the CSP maintain up-to-date all documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service?	-Document version control box up-to-date - Configuration management audit record
CS-06.2B	The documentation shall cover, at least, how the subnets are allocated, how the network is zoned and segmented, how it connects with third-party and public networks, and the	Q1-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how the subnets are allocated?	

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	geographical locations in which the cloud customers' data are stored			
		Q2-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how the network is zoned and segmented?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
		Q3-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how it connects with third-party and public networks?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
		Q4-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover the geographical locations in which the cloud customers' data are stored?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
CS-07.1B	The CSP shall ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data by suitable procedures when offering functions to CSCs for software-defined networking (SDN)	Q1-CS-07.1B	Does the CSP ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data by suitable procedures when offering functions to CSCs for software-defined networking (SDN)?	- Documented suitable procedures to ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data
CS-07.2B	The CSP shall validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs or modifying existing SDN features	Q1-CS-07.2B	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs?	- SDN functions validation record

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CS-07.2	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before modifying existing SDN features?	- SDN functions validation record
CS-08.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02	Q1-CS-08.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02?	- Documented policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards
			Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02?	- Communication mechanism: - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
			Does the CSP implement policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02?	- Audit records

Portability and Interoperability

Table 14. Checklist for PI basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PI-01.1B	The cloud service shall be accessible by cloud services from other CSPs or cloud customers' IT systems through documented inbound and outbound interfaces	Q1-PI-01.1B	Is the cloud service accessible by cloud services from other CSPs or cloud customers IT systems?	- accessible APIs - public URLs
		Q2-PI-01.1B	Are the inbound interfaces documented?	- Documented inbound interfaces (internal domain names)
		Q3-PI-01.1B	Are the outbound interfaces documented?	- Documented outbound interfaces
PI-01.2B	The interfaces shall be clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data	Q1-PI-01.2B	Are the interfaces clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data?	- Documented inbound and outbound interfaces (internal domain names and ports, mechanisms, username/pwd, etc) - Peer review of the documented interfaces
PI-01.3B	Communication on these interfaces shall use standardised communication protocols that ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted information according to its protection requirements and the adequate authentication of the user.	Q1-PI-01.3B	Does communication on these interfaces use standardized communication protocols?	- Documented list of supported communication protocols

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-PI-01.3B	Do protocols ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted information according to its protection requirements and the adequate authentication of the user?	- Documented list of supported communication protocols
PI-01.4B	Communication over untrusted networks shall be protected in confidentiality, integrity and authenticity according to CKM-02.	Q1-PI-01.4B	Is the communication over untrusted networks protected in confidentiality, integrity and authenticity according to CKM-02?	- Authentication and Protection Settings
PI-02.1B	The CSP shall include in cloud service contractual agreements, at least, the following aspects concerning the termination of the contractual relationship: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC; • Delivery methods of the data to the cloud customer; • Definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC; • Definition of the point in time as of which the CSP makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these; and • The CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data. 	Q1-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC)
		Q2-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include delivery methods of the data to the cloud customer?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include delivery methods of the data to the cloud customer)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC)
		Q4-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include definition of the point in time as of which the CSP makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include definition of the point in time as of which the CSP makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q5-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include the CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include the CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data)
PI-03.1B	The CSP shall implement procedures for deleting its customers' data upon termination of their contract in compliance with the contractual agreements between them	Q1-PI-03.1B	Does the CSP implement procedures for deleting its customers' data upon termination of their contract in compliance with the contractual agreements between them?	- Procedures for deleting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying the data deletion (successful / fail))
PI-03.2B	The CSC's data deletion shall include metadata and data stored in the data backups as well	Q1-PI-03.2B	Does the CSC's data deletion include metadata?	- Procedures for deleting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				the data deletion (successful / fail)
		Q2-PI-03.2B	Does the CSC's data deletion include data stored in the data backups?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Procedures for deteting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying the data deletion (successful / fail))
PI-03.3B	At the end of the contract, the CSP shall delete the technical data concerning the client.	Q1-PI-03.3B	At the end of a contract, does the CSP delete the technical data concerning the affected client?	- Technical data erasure records

Change and configuration management

Table 15. Checklist for CCM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CCM-01.1B	The CSP shall document, implement, and communicate policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service according to ISP-02	Q1-CCM-01.1B	Is there a document describing the policy for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Change management policy document
		Q2-CCM-01.1B	Are there documented procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Documented procedures for change management
		Q3-CCM-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate the defined policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q4-CCM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement the defined policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Change managements record & evidences - Audit records
CCM-02.1B	The CSP shall categorize and prioritize changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned	Q1-CCM-02.1B	Does the CSP categorize changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned?	- List of categorized changes
		Q2-CCM-02.1B	Does the CSP shall prioritize changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned?	- List of how changes are prioritized

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CCM-03.1B	The CSP shall test proposed changes before deployment	Q1-CCM-03.1B	Does the CSP test proposed changes before deployment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test plan ' - Tests (unit tests / continuous integration tests) - Documented test eXecution results
CCM-04.1B	The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment	Q1-CCM-04.1B	Is there defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment
		Q2-CCM-04.1B	Does the CSP use the defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidences of use the defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment - Audit records
CCM-05.1B	The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment.	Q1-CCM-05.1B	Does the CSP define roles for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of roles and the changes they are allowed to make and to which components
		Q2-CCM-05.1B	Does the CSP shall define rights for the defined roles according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - documented list of rights for each role

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CCM-05.2B	All changes to the cloud service in the production environment shall be logged and shall be traceable back to the individual or system component that initiated the change	Q1-CCM-05.2B	Are all changes to the cloud service in the production environment logged to the individual or system component that initiated the change?	- Log record of the session of the individual or system component that initiated the change
		Q2-CCM-05.2B	Are all changes to the cloud service in the production environment traceable back to the individual or system component that initiated the change?	- Log record of the session of the individual or system component that initiated the change
CCM-06.1B	The CSP shall implement version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes and to be able to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities.	Q1-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP document version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes?	- Documented version control procedures
		Q2-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP implement version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes?	- Documented list of dependencies of individual changes - Version control management tool - Tool for the management of binaries
		Q3-CCM-06.1B	Are the CSP document version control procedures able to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities?	- Documented version control procedures
		Q4-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP implement version control procedures that are able restore affected system components back to their previous state	- System tags - Version control tool

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
			as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities?	

Development of Information Systems

Table 16. Checklist for DEV basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DEV-01.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service.	Q1-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	- Documented policies and procedures
		Q2-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	- Safe development guides for each programming language used - Safety requirements in the design phase - Security checkpoints incorporated into project milestones

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Secure repositories - Security by design practices
DEV-01.2B	The policies and procedures for secure development shall consider information security from the earliest phases of design	Q1-DEV-01.2B	Do the policies for secure development consider information security from the earliest phases of design?	- Documented policies (encompasses information security from the earliest phases of design)
		Q2-DEV-01.2B	Do the procedures for secure development consider information security from the earliest phases of design?	- Documented procedures (encompass information security from the earliest phases of design)
DEV-02.1B	The CSP shall maintain a list of dependencies to hardware and software products used in the development of its cloud service	Q1-DEV-02.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of dependencies to hardware products used in the development of its cloud service?	- Documented list of dependencies to hardware products used in the development of its cloud service
		Q2-DEV-02.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of dependencies to software products used in the development of its cloud service?	- Documented list of dependencies to software products used in the development of its cloud service
DEV-03.1B	The CSP shall ensure that the confidentiality and integrity of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development	Q1-DEV-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that the confidentiality of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development?	- Source code protection policy (e.g. NDA, IPR, Licence)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-DEV-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that the integrity of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development?	- SAST and DAST results - security code checks -
DEV-03.2B	The CSP shall use version control to keep a history of the changes in source code with an attribution of changes to individual developers	Q1-DEV-03.2B	Does the CSP use version control to keep a history of the changes in source code?	- Version control tool in use
		Q2-DEV-03.2B	Is it maintained an attribution of changes to individual developers?	- Version control tool - Change log records
DEV-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from development, test or pre-production environments	Q1-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from development environments?	- Documented environments description
		Q2-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from testenvironments?	- Documented environments description
		Q3-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated frompre-production environments?	- Documented environments description
DEV-04.2B	Customer data contained in the production environments shall not be used in development, test or pre-production environments in order not to compromise their confidentiality.	Q1-DEV-04.2B	Customer data are not used in any other environment that is not the production environment? Does the CSP use different set of data, or encrypted customer data or modified customer data in test or pre-production environments?	- Data set used in test and pre-production environments
DEV-05.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate, make available and implement specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS	Q1-DEV-05.1B	Does the CSP document specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements?	- Documented specific procedures for the development of functions

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	scheme, with increased testing requirements.			
		Q2-DEV-05.1B	Does the CSP communicate specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements.	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-DEV-05.1B	Does the CSP make available specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements?	- Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB
		Q4-DEV-05.1	Does the CSP implement specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements?	- Technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements
DEV-06.1B	The CSP shall apply appropriate measures to check the cloud service for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the cloud service during the development process.	Q1-DEV-06.1B	Does the CSP apply appropriate measures to check the cloud service for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the cloud service during the development process?	- Vulnerability assessments results (manual)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DEV-06.2B	The procedures for identifying vulnerabilities shall be integrated in the development process.	Q1-DEV-06.2B	Are the procedures for identifying vulnerabilities integrated in the development process?	- Documented procedures for identifying vulnerabilities - Documented development process - Development process audit records
DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, the CSP and the contractor shall contractually agree on specifications regarding at least the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security in software development (requirements, design, implementation, tests and verifications) in accordance with recognised standards and methods; • Acceptance testing of the quality of the services provided in accordance with the agreed functional and non-functional requirements; and • Providing evidence that sufficient verifications have been carried out to rule out the existence of known vulnerabilities. 	Q1-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding at security in software development (requirements, design, implementation, tests and verifications) in accordance with recognised standards and methods?	- Contract signed by both parts
		Q2-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding at acceptance testing of the quality of the services provided in accordance with the agreed functional and non-functional requirements?	- Contract signed by both parts

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding a providing evidence that sufficient verifications have been carried out to rule out the existence of known vulnerabilities?	- Contract reviewed and signed by both parts

Procurement Management

Table 17. Checklist for PM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PM-01.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service	Q1-PM-01.1B	Is there a document describing the policy for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service?	-Controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service policy document
		Q2-PM-01.1B	Are there documented procedures for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented procedures for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-PM-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate the defined policies and procedures for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service?	- Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q4-PM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement the defined policies and procedures for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service?	- Records that demonstrate the control to third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service records & evidences (e.g.meeting minutes, monthly follow up reports)
PM-02.1B	The CSP shall perform a risk assessment of its suppliers in accordance with the policies and procedures for the control and monitoring of third parties before they start contributing to the provision of the cloud service	Q1-PM-02.1B	Does the CSP perform a risk assessment of its suppliers or the control and monitoring of third parties before they start contributing to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented risk assessment
		Q2-PM-02.1B	Is the risk assessment performed in accordance with the policies and procedures for the control and monitoring of third parties before they start contributing to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented risk assessment - Risk assessment review results
PM-02.2B	Following the risk assessment of a subservice provider, the CSP shall define for every applicable EUCS requirement a list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls	Q1-PM-02.2B	Following the risk assessment of a subservice provider, does the CSP define a list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls (CSOC) to be implemented by the subservice provider?	- Documented list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	(CSOC) to be implemented by the subservice provider			
		Q2-PM-02.2B	Is the list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls (CSOC) been defined for every applicable EUCS?	- Documented list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls - Documented list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls review results
PM-02.3B	The CSP shall ensure that the subservice provider has implemented the CSOCs, and that the subservice provider has made available evidence supporting the assessment of their effectiveness to the targeted evaluation level	Q1-PM-02.3B	Does the CSP ensure that the subservice provider has implemented the CSOCs?	- Subservice provider CSOC documented implementation results review - Audit report to the Subservice provider
		Q2-PM-02.3B	Does the CSP ensure that the subservice provider has made available evidence supporting the assessment of their effectiveness to the targeted evaluation level?	- Available evidence supporting the assessment of their effectiveness to the targeted evaluation level provided by the subservice provider
PM-02.4B	The adequacy of the risk assessment and of the definition of CSOCs shall be reviewed regularly, at least annually	Q1-PM-02.4B	Is the adequacy of the risk assessment reviewed regularly?	- Documented risk assessment review records (2/3 years)
		Q2-PM-02.4B	Is the adequacy of the definition of CSOCs reviewed regularly?	- Documented definition of CSOCs review
		Q3-PM-02.4B	Is the adequacy of the risk assessment reviewed at least annually?	- Risk assessment review version control and change history

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-PM-02.4B	Is the adequacy of the definition of CSOCs reviewed at least annually?	- Definition of CSOCs review version control and change history
PM-03.1B	The CSP shall maintain a directory for controlling and monitoring the suppliers who contribute to the delivery of the cloud service	Q1-PM-03.1B	Does the CSP maintain a directory for controlling and monitoring the suppliers who contribute to the delivery of the cloud service?	- Centralized directory of suppliers
PM-03.2B	The CSP shall verify the directory for completeness, accuracy and validity at least annually	Q1-PM-03.2B	Do the CSP shall verify the directory for completeness, accuracy and validity?	- Directory audit report
		Q2-PM-03.2B	The CSP shall verify the directory for completeness, accuracy and validity at least annually	- Directory audit report version control and change history
PM-04.1B	The CSP shall monitor the compliance of its suppliers with information security requirements and applicable legal and regulatory requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties	Q1-PM-04.1B	Does the CSP monitor the compliance of its suppliers with information security requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring
		Q2-PM-04.1B	Does the CSP monitor the compliance of its suppliers with applicable legal and regulatory requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring
PM-04.2B	The frequency of the monitoring shall correspond to the classification of the third party based on the risk assessment conducted by the Cloud Service Provider (cf. PM-02),	Q1-PM-04.2B	Does the frequency of the monitoring correspond to the classification of the third party based on the risk assessment conducted by the Cloud Service Provider?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoringt version control and change history

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	and the results of the monitoring shall be included in the review of the third party's risk assessment.			
		Q2-PM-04.2b	Are the results of the monitoring included in the review of the third party's risk assessment?	- Documented review of the third party's risk assessment
PM-04.3B	Identified violations and deviations shall be analysed, evaluated and treated in accordance with the risk management procedure (cf. RM-01)	Q1-PM-04.3	Are Identified violations and deviations analysed, in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
		Q2-PM-04.3	Are Identified violations and deviations evaluated in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
		Q3-PM-04.3	Are Identified violations and deviations treated in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
PM-04.4B	When a change in a third-party contributing to the delivery of the cloud service affects its level of security, the CSP shall inform all of its CSCs without undue delay	Q1-PM-04.4B	Does the CSP shall inform all of its CSCs without undue delay when a change in a third-party contributes to the delivery of the cloud service affects its level of security?	-Intranet/WEB -eMail - Etc.
PM-05.1B	The CSP shall define exit strategies for the purchase of services where the risk assessment of the suppliers identified a very high dependency	Q1-.PM-05.1B	Does the CSP define exit strategies for the purchase of services where the risk assessment of the suppliers identified a very high dependency?	- Documented exit strategies for the purchase of services

Incident Management

Table 18. Checklist for IM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IM-01.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 containing technical and organisational safeguards to ensure a fast, effective and proper response to all known security incidents, including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines for the classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management. 	Q1-IM-01.1B	Are the all known security incidents documented?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documented security incidents Guidelines for the classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management. security incidents communicated (a sample)
		Q2-IM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures containing technical and organisational safeguards to ensure a response to all known security incidents?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documented policies and procedures about security incidents management
		Q3-IM-01.1B	Does the documented technical and organisational safeguards ensure a fast, effective and proper response to all know security incidents?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical and organisational safeguards assessment result
		Q4-IM-01.1B	Are the previous policies and procedures aligned with the ISP-02 policy (Global Security Policy)and do they include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines for the classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross References between Global Security Policy and Security Incident management Policy

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management? 	
		Q5-IM-01.1B	Are the previous policies and procedures communicated?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mechanisms used to communicate the policies and procedures Intranet/WEB eMail Wallchart Specific meetings minutes Etc.
		Q6-IM-01.1B	Are the previous policies and procedures implemented?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Example of policy/procedures implementation randomly sampled
IM-01.2B	The CSP shall establish a point of contact, which contributes to the coordinated resolution of security incidents	Q1-IM-01.2B	Has the CSP established a point of contact, for a coordinated resolution of security incidents?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact point name
IM-02.1B	The CSP shall classify, prioritize, and perform root-cause analyses for events that could constitute a security incident, using their subject matter experts and external security providers where appropriate	Q1-IM-02.1B	For the events that could constitute a security incident, does the CSP perform root-cause analysis?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Security Incidents database Root-Cause Analysis result document Root-cause analysis
		Q2-IM-02.1B	Are the root causes classified?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Root-Cause Analysis result document
		Q3-IM-02.1B	Are the root-causes prioritized?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Root-Cause Analysis result document
		Q4-IM-02.1B	In the root-analysis sessions are the subject matter experts involved?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Root-Cause Analysis result document

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q5-IM-02.1B	In the root-analysis sessions are external security providers involved where appropriate?	- Root-Cause Analysis result document
IM-03.1B	The CSP shall document the implemented measures after a security incident has been processed and, following the contractual agreements, the document shall be sent to the affected customers for final acknowledgment or, if applicable, as confirmation.	Q1-IM-03.1B	Does the CSP document the implemented measures after a security incident root-cause analysis?	- Documented measures derived from the root-cause analysis
		Q2-IM-03.1B	The document has been sent to the affected customers, following the correspondent contractual agreement for final acknowledgment/confirmation?	- Security Incident newsletter/document for the customers
		Q3-IM-03.1B	Have the affected customers provided a final acknowledge of reception of the previous document and when applicable a confirmation?	- Ack/Confirmation from customers of the previous newsletter
IM-03.2B	The CSP shall make information on security incidents or confirmed security breaches available to all affected customers	Q1-IM-03.2B	Does the CSP make information on security incidents or confirmed security breaches available to all affected customers?	Information mechanism used -WEB -eMail - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q2-IM-03.2B	Does the CSP send information of security incidents to all the documented affected customers?	- Security Incident Newsletter for each affected customers

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IM-04.1B	The CSP shall inform employees and external business partners of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service	Q1-IM-04.1B	Does the CSP inform employees of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q2-IM-04.1B	Does the CSP inform external business partners of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
IM-04.2B	The CSP shall not take any negative action against those who communicate "false reports" of events that do not subsequently turn out to be incidents, and shall make that policy known as part of its communication to employees and external business partners	Q1-IM-04.2B	Does the security incident management policy contain an explicit mention that the CSP not take any negative action against those who communicate "false reports" of events that do not subsequently turn out to be incidents?	- Security incident management policy
		Q2-IM-04.2B	Is the previous policy communicated to employees?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-IM-04.2B	Is the previous policy communicated to external business partners?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
IM-04.3B	The CSP shall define, publish and implement a single point of contact to report security events and vulnerabilities	Q1-IM-04.3B	Has the CSP established a single point of contact to report security events?	Documented Role and Responsibilities related to the Security Incidents Manager/Collector
		Q2-IM-04.3B	Is the single point of contact made public?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-IM-04.3B	Is the single point of contact operative?	- List of security incident received and managed by the single point of contact
IM-05.1B	The CSP shall periodically inform its customers on the status of the incidents affecting the CSC, or, where appropriate and necessary, involve them in the resolution, according to the contractual agreements	Q1-IM-05.1B	Does the CSP periodically inform customers on the status of the incidents affecting the CSC?	- Security Incident Newsletter / periodic communication to customers
		Q2-IM-05.1B	Where appropriate and necessary, does the CSP involve customers in the incidents resolution according to the contractual agreements?	- Requests of participations in incidents analysis - Contractual Agreements
IM-05.2B	As soon as an incident has been closed, The CSP shall inform its customers about the actions taken, according to the contractual agreements	Q1-IM-05.2B	As soon as an incident has been closed, does the CSP inform the cus-	- Security Incident Newsletter - Contractual Agreements

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
			tomers about the actions taken, according to the contractual agreements?	
IM-06.1B	The CSP shall perform an analysis of security incidents to identify recurrent or significant incidents and to identify the need for further protection, if needed with the support of external bodies	Q1-IM-06.1B	Does the CSP perform a security incidents analysis to identify recurrent and/or significant incidents?	- Security Incident Data Base with the classification of recurrent and significant incident
		Q2-IM-06.1B	In case of recurrent or significant incidents detected, does the CSP identify need for further protection?	- Documented further protection associated to recurrent and significant incidents
		Q3-IM-06.1	Does the CSP involve external bodies if necessary?	- Contracts with external bodies
IM-06.2B	The CSP shall only contract supporting external bodies that are qualified incident response service providers or government agencies	Q1-IM-06.2B	Are the external bodies contracted "qualified incident response service providers or "government agencies"?	- Qualifications of the contracted external bodies
IM-07.1B	The CSP shall document and implement a procedure to archive all documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents	Q1-IM-07.1B	Does the CSP document a procedure to archive all documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents?	- Documented procedure to archive security incidents
		Q2-IM-07.1B	Is the previous documented procedure implemented?	- Example of security incidents documentation randomly selected
IM-07.2B	The CSP shall implement security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents in accordance with criticality levels and legal requirements in effect	Q1-IM-07.2B	Does the CSP implement security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents?	- Example of security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents randomly sampled
		Q2-IM-07.2B	Are the implemented security mechanism and processes in accordance with criticality levels and legal requirements in effect	

Business Continuity

Table 19. Checklist for BC basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
BC-01.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and make available policies and procedures establishing the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency management	Q1-BC-01.1B	Has the CSP documented policies and procedures to ensure business continuity and contingency?	- Documented policies and procedures related to business continuity and contingency
		Q2-BC-01.1B	Does the documented policies and procedures establish the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency?	- Documented policies and procedures related to business continuity and contingency (encompasses the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency)
		Q3-BC-01.1B	Have the previous documented policies and procedures been communicated within the organization?	Communication mechanisms used - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-BC-01.1B	Have the previous documented policies and procedures been made available?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - Etc. Depending on the "how" were made available, randomly chosen examples
BC-02.1B	The policies and procedures for business continuity and contingency management shall include the need to perform a business impact analysis to determine the impact of any malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise.	Q1-BC-02.1B	Does the CSP document all the possible malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise?	- Documented list of all the possible malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise
		Q2-BC-02.1B	Does the business continuity and contingency management policies and procedure contain the need to perform a business impact analysis related to all the documented malfunctions?	- Business continuity and contingency management policies and procedures (encompass the need to perform a business impact analysis related to all the documented malfunctions)
BC-03.1B	The CSP shall document and implement a business continuity plan and contingency plans to ensure continuity of the services, taking into account information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis	Q1-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP document a business continuity plan?	- Business Continuity Plan
		Q2-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP document a contingency plan to ensure continuity of the services?	- Contingency Plan

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-BC-03.1B	Does the documented business continuity plan take into account information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Business Continuity Plan (encompasses information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis) - Business Continuity Plan review
		Q4-BC-03.1B	Does the documented contingency plan take into account information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contingency Plan (encompasses information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis) - Contingency Plan Review
		Q5-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP implement the business continuity plan?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - According with the business continuity plan requirements, execution evidences randomly selected
		Q6-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP implement the contingency plan?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - According with the contingency plan requirements, execution evidences randomly selected

Compliance

Table 20. Checklist for CO basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CO-01.1B	The CSP shall document the legal, regulatory, self-imposed and contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service	Q1-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the legal requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the legal requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
		Q2-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the regulatory requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (the regulatory requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
		Q3-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the self-imposed requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the self-imposed requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP shall document the contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
CO-02.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate, make available and implement policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits, made in accordance with ISP-02. **Audits should be comprehensive to the IT control environment, with a frequency of auditing certain elements of the audit universe according to their risk level, identified by risk assessment.**	Q1-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audit policy document - Audit planning and conducting procedures
		Q2-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - eMail - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		Q3-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP make available policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q4-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	- Audit plan - Audit report - Documented list of nonconformities
CO-03.1B	The CSP shall perform at regular intervals and at least annually internal audits by subject matter experts to check the compliance of their internal security control system to the requirements defined in CO-01 and to the requirements of the EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level.	Q1-CO-03.1B	Does the CSP perform audits to check the compliance of their internal security control system to the requirements defined?	- Audit plan - Audit report - Documented list of nonconformities
		Q2-CO-03.1B	Are the internal audits performed by subject matter experts?	- Internal auditor's training records
		Q3-CO-03.1B	Are the internal audits performed at least annually?	- Documented audit plan
		Q4-CO-03.1B	Does the internal audit check the compliance to the requirements defined in CO1 and to the requirements of the EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level?	- Internal audit reports and/or checklist aligned with EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level
CO-03.2B	The CSP shall document specifically deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements, including an assessment of their severity, and keep track of their remediation	Q1-CO-03.2B	Does the CSP document specifically deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements?	- Audit report - Documented list of deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-CO-03.2B	Do the documented deviations include an assessment of their severity?	- Documented list of deviations including an assessment of their severity
		Q3-CO-03.2B	Does the CSP keep track of their remediation?	- Monitoring report of the nonconformities from the EUCS requirements remediation
CO-04.1B	The CSP shall regular inform its top management about the information security performance within the scope of the internal control system.	Q1-CO-04.1B	Does the CSP regular inform its top management about the information security performance within the scope of the internal control system?	- Information security performance report to top management - eMail - Other specific document

User documentation

Table 21. Checklist for DOC basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DOC-01.1B	The CSP shall make publicly available guidelines and recommendations to assist the Cloud Service Users with the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the cloud service provided	Q1-DOC-01.1B	Does the CSP make publicly available guidelines and recommendations to assist the Cloud Service Users?	- Guidelines - Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - Etc.

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deal with the secure configuration of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure configuration of the cloud service provided)
		Q3-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deal with the secure installation of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure installation of the cloud service provided)
		Q4-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deal with the secure deployment of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure deployment of the cloud service provided)
		Q5-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deal with the secure operation of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure operation of the cloud service provided)
		Q6-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deals with the secure maintenance of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure maintenance of the cloud service provided)
		Q7-DOC-01.1B	Do the guidelines and recommendations deals with the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the cloud service provided?	- Guidelines (encompass the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the cloud service provided)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DOC-01.2B	The CSP shall maintain guidelines and recommendations applicable to the cloud service in the version intended for productive use	Q1-DOC-01.2B	Does the CSP maintain guidelines and recommendations applicable to the cloud service in the version intended for productive use?	- Guidelines and recommendations - version control and change history
DOC-02.1B	The CSP shall operate or refer to a publicly available and daily updated online register of known vulnerabilities that affect the provided cloud service	Q1-DOC-02.1B	Does the CSP operate or refer to a publicly available online register of known vulnerabilities that affect the provided cloud service?	- Online register of known vulnerabilities (Web, e-mail)
		Q2-DOC-02.1B	Is the online register of known vulnerabilities daily updated?	- Web page updated date - e-mail sent date
DOC-03.1B	The CSP shall provide comprehensible and transparent information on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Its jurisdiction; and • System component locations, including its subcontractors, where the cloud customer's data is processed, stored and backed up. 	Q1-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on its jurisdiction?	-Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly '-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail
		Q2-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on system component locations?	-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail '-Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on its subcontractors?	-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail '-Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly
		Q4-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on where the cloud customer's data is processed, stored and backed up?	-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail '-Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly
		Q5-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information about the on where the cloud customer's data is processed, stored and backed up?	Service Catalogue Other internal Documentation '-Contractual agreement: it shall indicate where the data is processed, stored and backed up
DOC-03.2B	The CSP shall provide sufficient information for subject matter experts of the CSC to determine to assess the suitability of the cloud service's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective	Q1-DOC-03.2B	Does the CSP provide sufficient information for subject matter experts of the CSC to determine to assess the suitability of the cloud service's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective?	Service Catalogue Other internal Documentation '-Contractual agreement: it shall indicate where the data is processed, stored and backed up
DOC-04.1B	The CSP shall provide a justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification, based on the risks associated to the cloud service's targeted users and use cases	Q1-DOC-04.1B	Does the CSP provide a justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification?	- Documented justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-DOC-04.1B	Is the justification based on the risks associated to the cloud service's targeted users?	- Documented justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification (based on the risks associated to the cloud service's targeted users)
		Q3-DOC-04.1B	Is the justification based on the use cases?	- Documented justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification (based on the use cases)
DOC-04.2B	If the CSP claims compliance to security profiles for its cloud service, the justification shall cover the security profiles.	Q1-DOC-04.2B	If the CSP claims compliance to security profiles for its cloud service, does the justification cover the security profiles?	- Documented justification for the assurance level targeted in the certification (cover the security profiles)
DOC-04.3B	A summary of the justification shall be made publicly available as part of the certification package, which shall allow CSCs to perform a high-level analysis about their own use cases	Q1-DOC-04.3B	Is there a summary of the justification made publicly available as part of the certification package?	-Summary of the justification made publicly available
		Q2-DOC-04.3B	Does the summary allow CSCs to perform a high-level analysis about their own use cases?	-Summary of the justification
DOC-05.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, does the CSP develop specific documentation and make it available to CSCs (upon request), based on the Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs) that they have defined?	Q1-DOC-05.1B	If the CSP expects CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on its cloud service using composition, does the CSP provide specific documentation based on the Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs) that they have defined?	- Specific documentation based on the Complementary Customer Controls (CCCs)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DOC-05.2B	The CSP shall make this documentation available to CSCs upon request.	Q1-DOC-05.2B	Does the CSP make this documentation available to CSCs upon request?	- CSS documentation request - Record of submission of the required documentation - e-mail - other
DOC-06.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, it shall document for each EUCS requirement how its cloud service will contribute (if any) to the fulfilment of the requirement by the cloud service developed by the CSC using the CSP as subservice organization.	Q1-DOC-06.1B	Does the CSP document for each EUCS requirement how its cloud service will contribute (if any) to the fulfilment of the requirement by the cloud service developed by the CSC using the CSP as subservice organization?	-
DOC-06.2B	The CSP shall make this documentation available to cloud customers upon request	Q1-DOC-06.2B	Does the CSP make the documentation defined in DOC-06.1 available to cloud customers upon request?	- CSS documentation request - Record of submission of the required documentation - e-mail - other

Investigative Inquires

Table 22. Checklist for INQ basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
INQ-01.1B	The CSP shall subject investigation requests from government agencies to a legal assessment by subject matter experts	Q1-INQ-01.1B	Does the CSP execute a legal assessment of every investigation requests received from government agencies?	- Legal assessment results

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q2-INQ-01.1B	Is the assessor and expert of the subject matter?	- Assessor documented qualifications
INQ-01.2B	The legal assessment shall determine whether the government agency has an applicable and legally valid basis and what further steps need to be taken	Q1-INQ-01.2B	Does the government agency that sent the request has an applicable and legally valid basis?	-
		Q2-INQ-01.2B	Does the legal assessment results contain the further steps need to be taken in response of the investigation request received?	- Legal assessment results (contain the further steps need to be taken in response of the investigation request received)
INQ-02.1B	The CSP shall inform the affected CSC(s) without undue delay, unless the applicable legal basis on which the government agency is based prohibits this or there are clear indications of illegal actions in connection with the use of the cloud service	Q1-INQ-02.1B	Does the CSP inform without undue delay the affected CSC(s) about the received investigation requests?	- Documented notice sent to every CSC affected by the investigation request. This document must include the delivery date
		Q2-INQ-02.1B	In case CSP did not inform the affected CSC(s) was because the applicable legal basis on which the government agency is based prohibits this or because there are clear indications of illegal actions in connection with the use of the cloud service?	- Investigation Request + Legal Assessment Results
INQ-03.1B	The CSP shall only provide access to or disclose cloud customer data in the context of government investigation requests after the CSP's legal assessment (cf. INQ-01) has shown that an applicable	Q1-INQ-03.1B	Has the CSP provided access to or disclose customer data to government agency only after the legal assessment has shown that an applicable and valid legal basis exists?	- ecord of the data in which CSP has provided access to customer data to the government agency + Assessment Results

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
	and valid legal basis exists and that the investigation request must be granted on that basis.			
INQ-03.2B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to ensure that government agencies only have access to the data they need to investigate	Q1-INQ-03.2B	Does the CSP document procedures to ensure that government agencies only have access to the data they need to investigate?	- Documented procedure that describe the mechanism to provide access to customer data to government agency by limiting the scope to only that data they need to investigate according to the investigation request
		Q2-INQ-03.2B	Does the CSP implement the documented procedures to to ensure that government agencies only have access to the data they need to investigate?	- Examples of Investigation Requests+Data needed for the investigation+evidences that the access has been authorized ONLY to that data

Product Safety and security

Table 23. Checklist for PSS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PSS-01.1B	The CSP shall offer to their CSCs error handling and logging mechanisms that allow them to obtain security-related information about the security status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides	Q1-PSS-01.1B	Does the CSP offer to their CSCs error handling mechanisms?	- Error handling mechanism instantiated to every customer
		Q2-PSS-01.1B	Does error handling mechanisms allow customers to obtain security-related information about the security status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides?	- Operation manual of the error handling mechanism
		Q3-PSS-01.1B	Does the CSP offer to their CSCs logging mechanisms?	- Logging mechanism instantiated to every customer
		Q4-PSS-01.1B	Does logging mechanisms allow customers to obtain security-related information about the security status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides?	- Operation manual of the logging mechanism
PSS-02.1B	A state-of-the-art session management system shall be used that is suitably protected against known attacks	Q1-PSS-02.1B	Is a state-of-the-art session management system used? Is it protected against known attacks?	- Session management system description (functional)

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PSS-03.1B	The CSP shall ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data by suitable procedures when offering functions for software-defined networking (SDN)	Q1-PSS-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data by suitable procedures when offering functions for software-defined networking (SDN)?	- Documented procedures
PSS-03.2B	The CSP shall validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs or modifying existing SDN features	Q1-PSS-03.2B	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs	- Validation Report
		Q2-PSS-03.2B	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before modifying existing SDN features to CSCs?	- Validation Report
PSS-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure the following aspects if CSCs operate virtual machines or containers with the cloud service: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CSC can restrict the selection of images of virtual machines or containers according to his specifications, so that users of this CSC can only launch the images or containers released according to these restrictions. • In addition, these images provided by the CSP are hardened according to generally accepted industry standards. 	Q1-PSS-04.1B	When the CSC operates virtual machine, does the CSP ensure that the CSC can restrict the selection of images of virtual machines according to his specifications?	-Authorization authentication procedures to access containers and the registry where they are stored
		Q2-PSS-04.1B	When the CSC operates container, does the CSP ensure that the CSC can restrict the selection of images of containers according to his specifications?	-Authorization authentication procedures to access containers and the registry where they are stored

ReqID [3]	Requirement [3]	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
		Q3-PSS-04.1B	Are the images provided by the CSP hardened according to generally accepted industry standards?	-

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